

LOOKING AT STUDENT-TEACHER FORMAL CORRESPONDENCE THROUGH THE LENS OF COLLEGE INSTRUCTORS: A PHENOMENOLOGY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 29

Issue 6

Pages: 844-885

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2792

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14561372

Manuscript Accepted: 11-22-2024

Looking at Student-Teacher Formal Correspondence through the Lens of College Instructors: A Phenomenology

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Abstract

This phenomenological study aims to explore, understand, and look at the lived experiences of college instructors in student-teacher formal correspondence. Through purposive sampling, 14 college instructors with a minimum of 3 years' experience at KCAST were selected for participation. All of them participated in the in-depth interviews. Results revealed the experiences of the participants: having language barriers towards effective communication, crossing the line between teacher and student relationships, extending service beyond the working hours, struggling in the absence of proper etiquette in dealing with teachers, experiencing a lack of respect from students, and having message misinterpretation on an online platform. In response to the challenges they have encountered, they deem the following coping strategies essential: setting clear expectations at the beginning of a course or program, correcting improper behavior immediately, establishing boundaries and authority in the class, building good rapport through a supportive teacher-student relationship, having an understanding of the various underlying reasons for students' misbehaviors, implementing a policy of language used inside the classroom, and strengthening student-teacher communication through comprehensive feedback. Upon reflecting on their entire experience, they arrived at the following insights: to lead is to set by example; the importance of open communication and a sense of empathy; the value of cultivating good connections through understanding, consideration, and openness; upholding professionalism and respect with each other; and building a healthy relationship in the learning environment. The results of this study were anticipated to be meaningful and important to the participants, instructors, students, and researchers.

Keywords: *college instructors, student-teacher formal correspondence, phenomenology, Philippines*

Introduction

Establishing a positive rapport between teachers and students within the classroom is essential, as it signifies an effort to build mutual trust and respect. Unlike casual communication interactions, the communication between instructors and students is grounded in a formal relationship, necessitating adherence to the norms and principles of the teaching profession. However, cultivating this partnership requires active participation from both parties. Instructors often encounter challenges in connecting with students personally, and students may struggle with unresolved language or speech issues, leading to ineffective communication. Instructors and students, like others, confront a variety of communication challenges. Therefore, the absence of formal correspondence in student-teacher communication can give rise to a range of issues, including errors, lack of respect, frustration, misunderstanding, or even misinterpretation (Vanner, 2022).

In Indonesia, particularly at the University of Surabaya, slang language has been particularly articulated, which decreases the quality of Indonesian language formalism. The Education Minister of Indonesia has maintained that the level of politeness among Indonesian students is deteriorating. Many students now exhibit impolite speech and tend to favor the use of slang or informal language within the school environment. Consequently, it becomes the teacher's duty to impart the skill of speaking politely to their students and to provide guidance when impolite language is used, particularly during classroom interactions. Furthermore, teachers must set an example by consistently employing polite language when addressing students, aiming to inspire them to adopt similar politeness in their own speech (Nuh, 2012; Mariani, 2017; Herdarajat et al., 2023).

Recently, in the Philippines, particularly in the universities in Metro Manila, English has consistently held the status of an official language, being spoken by over 14 million Filipinos. Despite English being classified as a second language in the Philippines, most Filipino students often encounter difficulties when attempting to communicate formally using the English language, and they frequently refrain from speaking due to psychological obstacles, a lack of appropriate vocabulary and expressions, or language anxiety. Consequently, this may result in more informal and casual forms of communication (Annie, 2019; Jugo, 2020; Genelza, 2022).

In addition, the examination of college instructors' experiences in their formal communication with students has immense social significance, as this can be a scholarly basis for the improvement of formal communication, as it can aid institutions in optimizing their educational methods, serve as a framework for efficient information exchange, aid both students and instructors in enhancing their communication skills, and cultivate a more inclusive, positive rapport, leading to a more effective learning environment. Such a study is adequately urgent, as the insights contributes to the college instructors which can offer valuable input for educational institutions and students and promote effective communication, which helps prepare and equipping students for professional interactions and collaboration in their future careers. This input can be used to pinpoint areas where formal communication programs may require enhancements. Thus, the purpose of this study is to extend benefits to both educators and students, ultimately elevating the quality of higher education.

In this connection, given the seriousness of the situation, previous research has been conducted to investigate the issue, identify its root cause, and offer recommendations and solutions. The study by Albawi and Nadeem (2020), titled “Exploring the Impact of Ineffective Formal Communication between Teachers and Students: A Case Study of Mustaqbal University and Jubail University College, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia,” specifically explores the barriers hindering effective communication between teachers and students in EFL programs within the classroom. Moreover, Batubara’s (2022) study, titled “The Correlation between EFL Students’ Self-Confidence and English-Speaking Anxiety at Pasifik Morotai University,” focused on examining the link between students’ English-speaking anxiety and their self-confidence. Additionally, Kirinic’s (2021) research, titled “The Correlations among the Dimensions of Teachers’ Communication Styles and Communication Etiquette,” aimed to explore the various aspects of teacher’s communication styles. This study provided an in-depth analysis of how a teacher’s behavior affects their communication style and gave a thorough analysis of the student-teacher communication. However, these studies did not explore the lived experiences of the college instructors in their student-teacher formal correspondence. Thus, the focus of the current study is on the lived experiences of the college instructors in student-teacher formal correspondence. This aspect, which examines the challenges and experiences of college instructors and provides valuable insights into the details of formal communication from the lens of college instructors, represents the research gap that this study seeks to address.

As a result, this study aims to share important findings with key groups to improve communication in local colleges. The main audiences include college instructors, administrators, students, and researchers. Instructors will learn how formal communication affects their relationships with students, while administrators can use the results to improve communication guidelines at their colleges. Students will also benefit by better understanding what’s expected in formal correspondence. Researchers can build on the study to explore pedagogical communication further. Dissemination will occur through printed copies of the research and published in academic journals..

Research Questions

The purpose of this phenomenological study is to explore and describe the experiences, difficulties, coping mechanisms, and insights related to student-teacher formal correspondence as seen through the lens of the college instructors at a local college in Kapalong, Davao del Norte. This study involved in-depth interviews and analysis of the experiences of instructors in this specific context. This study particularly sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of teachers in their formal correspondence with the students?
2. How do the teachers cope with the challenges in their formal correspondence with the students?
3. What are your insights of teachers about formal correspondence with students that they can share with others?

Methodology

Research Design

This qualitative study utilized a phenomenological approach. As per Bhandari (2023), qualitative research is a type of research that explores and provides deeper insights into real-world problems. It involves collecting and analyzing non-numerical data (e.g., text, video, or audio) to understand concepts, opinions, or experiences. It can be used to gather in-depth insights into a problem or generate new ideas for research. Moreover, this research design will gather participants’ experiences, perceptions, and behaviors. It answers the hows and whys instead of how many or how much.

In this study, the researcher used qualitative design to understand the lived experiences of the college instructors in their formal correspondence with students. By conducting interviews, I was able to capture the personal stories and perspectives of the instructors. This approach is effective for exploring their experiences in depth, allowing me to understand the details of their interactions and the meaning they attach to them. Furthermore, qualitative design is well-suited for this study because it helps reveal the complexities of how instructors communicate with their students.

In the meantime, phenomenology was utilized, which seeks to explore individuals’ daily experiences while setting aside the researchers’ prior assumptions about the phenomenon. In essence, phenomenological research examines lived experiences to gain a deeper understanding of how people perceive and interpret those experiences, focusing on their emotions, perceptions, and beliefs to uncover the core essence of the phenomenon being studied (Delve & Limpaecher, 2022).

In this study, the researcher utilized phenomenology, which is greatly suitable for this academic endeavor. Given the fact that the study only aims to account for the lived experiences of the participants in this study, who were the college instructors at KCAST, which allowed her to engage in flexible activities that can describe and help to understand complex phenomena.

Participants

The main participants in this study were the college instructors at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology in Davao del Norte. Fourteen participants were carefully selected for this research endeavor and undergone in-depth interviews (IDI), wherein each of them will be interviewed individually.

In determining the number of research participants, the researchers followed the recommendation of Creswell (1998) that there must be at least 5 to 25 participants in a qualitative study. These individuals were selected because their experiences and perspectives are directly relevant to the phenomenon being studied. Maintaining the ethical integrity of the research also required that the participants' participation be voluntary, anonymous, and confidential.

Upon participant selection, the researcher used purposive sampling to ensure that only those who could provide the necessary data would become the key participants of this study. During the recruitment process, the researcher diligently followed the specified criteria: (a) participants must be college instructors who have worked for at least three years to have more experience with student-teacher communication at a specific local college, Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology; (b) each participant should have direct and considerable experience with formal student-teacher correspondence; (c) participants are willing and able to openly share their experiences with formal student-teacher correspondence.

Procedure

The data collection process involved a series of sequential steps. Initially, the researcher sought permission from the research adviser and the research technical panel and subsequently obtained approval from the panelists. Once these permissions were granted, the researcher began the construction of a research roadmap. During this phase, the researcher extensively reviewed various research studies related to formality in communication to acquire a comprehensive understanding of the topic, particularly the work of notable scholars in the field.

Secondly, the researcher provided a letter for the selected participants, requesting their consent to participate in the study. Once the approval letter from the panel was received, the researcher proceeded with conducting the study. But before officially conducting the interviews, the researcher oriented the participants. The researcher explained the purpose of the study, the focus, the methodology, and the rights of the participants during the interview. Additionally, the researcher asks for permission to record the entire interview.

After completing the interviews, all recorded sessions' data related to the experiences that the participants had given was treated in a discreet and anonymous manner. The recorded data was transcribed and then verified by the participants. Once the verification process was finished, the researcher proceeded to translate the data. The findings derived from the data analysis were used to draw conclusions and make recommendations based on the study.

Data Analysis

In the analysis of the data, the collected information in this research is both presented and scrutinized according to the requirements and goals of this research study. This process involved a comprehensive understanding and analysis of the content within the participants' responses, ultimately leading to the discovery of study findings.

Hence, in line with Ivan (2021), qualitative data analysis can be described as the procedure of collecting, organizing, and interpreting qualitative data to comprehend its significance. It involves non-numeric and unorganized data, typically encompassing textual elements like open-ended question responses or interviews, although it can extend to audio, images, and video as well. These findings will be obtained through questionnaires, interviews, or observations. The analysis of qualitative data empowers us to delve into concepts and offer deeper insights that complement quantitative findings.

In the context of this study, the data from selected college instructors at Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology was the main focus of the analysis. The researcher started by transcribing each interview word for word to capture all the details of the participants' experiences. To keep the analysis unbiased, the researcher made sure to set aside personal opinions and focused entirely on the participants' perspectives. Followed by identifying and coding key phrases and ideas that provided deeper insights into student-teacher formal correspondence. This careful process helped the researcher extract the core meaning of the participants' experiences, forming the basis for the study's findings.

Meanwhile, thematic analysis was employed as the chosen method. Thematic analysis is an approach to analyzing qualitative data that entails reviewing a dataset and identifying meaningful patterns and themes within it. It's essential to emphasize that this process is guided by the research objectives and questions, eliminating the need to identify every conceivable theme in the data, but instead concentrating on the critical aspects that pertain to your research questions (Crosley, 2021).

In the context of this study, the researcher utilized thematic analysis to uncover the deeper meanings of the experiences of the college instructors and identify the commonalities and unique experiences of the individuals involved. After completing the thematic analysis, the researcher developed core ideas from the coded data. Each core idea was carefully formulated and grouped into themes, with each theme having at least three core ideas to ensure accuracy. These themes, along with their core ideas, formed the results of the study.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure the proper conduct of this research as well as the safety of those involved in this undertaking, the researcher thoroughly conforms to the highest ethical standards suggested by Mack et al. (2005). This includes the following components: respect for persons, beneficence, justice, confidentiality, and consent.

The first principle, respect for persons, pertains to treating people as competent to make their own decision while acknowledging those who cannot make decision that require extensive consideration. It acknowledges each person as an autonomous, unique, and independent individual, emphasizing that every individual possesses the right and ability to make their own decisions. By respecting an individual, their dignity is upheld, and they are afforded the autonomy to make choices with access to all necessary information to make informed decisions (Scranton, 2020).

In the conduct of this study, the researcher established courtesy and rapport with the participants. The researcher provided an informed consent form and made sure to get permission before recording the conversations and responses. The researcher also ensured that participants understood that their involvement was voluntary and not forced in any way. Hence, their signatures on the consent form signified their voluntary willingness to participate.

The second principle, beneficence, emphasized that the research should have a positive impact and should not pose any risks to the individuals involved in the study (Kirsh, 2019; National Commission for the Protection of Human Subjects of Biomedical and Behavioral Research, 1978). Therefore, it was anticipated that the outcomes of this study would bring about favorable outcomes for the participants involved in this endeavor.

College instructors and students have benefited from this study. The results have served to improve communication strategies and build a stronger relationship between instructors and students, ultimately building good rapport with students through clear and respectful communication and fostering a more positive and productive learning environment. In addition, to ensure the safety and comfort of all selected college instructors, the researcher also identified a secure location for conducting interviews. Specifically, the interview was held in their respective offices. The information obtained was kept private and secure to prevent psychological risks such as shame, embarrassment, or other negative outcomes.

The third principle, justice, acknowledges that researchers should treat their research participants equitably, with the well-being of participants always taking precedence over the study's objectives. Adhering to this principle may pose challenges for researchers, particularly when ensuring that all participants, regardless of their perceived level of dependence, can derive benefits from the study. Justice guarantees the equitable allocation of advantages and responsibilities, with a focus on preventing any form of exploitation among participants. The initial step in upholding justice involves selecting participants based on the study's specific requirements rather than mere availability. This approach has been employed in implementation research to ensure the appropriate selection of research subjects (King, 2018).

In order to avoid any bias, the researcher, maintained impartiality and treated all participants with fairness and respect throughout the research process. Each participant received equal and comprehensive information regarding the potential risks and benefits as associated with the study. Moreover, the researcher gave meaningful tokens to each participant as a form of appreciation for their valuable contributions to the completion of this study. More importantly, the researcher made sure that only their relevant and accurate responses were included in my study.

Confidentiality was diligently upheld in this study. It signifies a mutual understanding established between the researcher and participants through the informed consent procedure. This understanding ensures that the participant's identity, personal data, responses, and so forth will not be divulged to any external parties, except in cases where alternative agreements are reached. Participants were duly informed that confidentiality might not be assured when identifiable information was being collected, and they were provided with details regarding the storage of their information both during and after the study (Holland, 2019).

To fulfill this requirement, the preservation of confidentiality and the anonymity of research participants were rigorously maintained throughout the data collection and analysis phases. The researcher took measures to hide their identities, including their names and programs. Pseudonyms were also used by the selected college instructors. In addition, their names and other identifying information were kept in separate, secure files. Furthermore, the research data were archived and scheduled for deletion three years following the study's completion.

The final principle is consent, which is a fundamental cornerstone of research ethics. Its fundamental purpose is to ensure that human participants willingly and voluntarily engage in research, having been fully informed about the implications of their participation, and that they provide their consent before joining the research. This consent should be obtained prospectively, meaning before the participant becomes involved in the research, and there must be no undue pressure or influence placed on participants to obtain their consent. At a minimum, informed consent requires that participants possess an understanding of the nature of the research and what they are agreeing to (Oxford, 2021).

Moreover, in this study, the principle of consent was diligently observed throughout the course. The researcher took great care to honor the participants' autonomy, ensuring that their participation was entirely voluntary and that they were fully informed about the study. The researcher also aimed to create a positive and comfortable environment for them both before and after their participation. Additionally, the researcher informed the participants that they had the right to ask questions during the interview. They also have the right to decline answering sensitive questions, specifically their experiences with regards to the student-teacher formal correspondence, to leave the interview without providing any explanation, and to be informed about the study results. In doing so, the researcher respected the decisions made by the participants.

Results and Discussion

This section was divided into four parts. Part one, focuses on the participant's data, from which the qualitative data were collected. Part two covers the data analysis procedures and the steps in categorizing the emergent themes from the results of the in-depth interviews. Part three deals with the responses to the interview questions pertaining to each research problem. Lastly, part four provides a summary of the responses.

Participants

The participants of this study were the college instructors at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology in Kapalong, Davao del Norte. As shown in Table 1, a total of 14 individuals took part in this study, comprising 14 participants for the in-depth interview.

In-depth Interview. There were fourteen key participants in this study. All of these participants were college instructors located in Kapalong, Davao del Norte. To uphold the principle of confidentiality, each participant was assigned a pseudonym during the in-depth interview, as used by Bernal (2014). The assignment of pseudonyms was made according to their unique characteristics and attitudes that were shown during the interview sessions.

For instance, Gentle got his nickname due to his attitude towards dealing with his students. He provides guidance and instruction in a gentle, nurturing manner, which fosters a sense of trust, comfort, and supportive environment among his students. Kindhearted was named for his warmth and generosity. His approach to his students makes them feel valued, understood and respected. Compassionate caretaker was named because she showed sympathy, support, affection, and a deep sense of care and concern for the needs and challenges of her students. Attentive observer received her nickname due to her attentiveness of students showing misbehavior, while also understanding the underlying reasons behind student's action before putting judgement and addressing issues that arise. Nurturing was chosen for the participant because of his characteristics as a gardener who nurtures his students to be and act like this while also providing care and support to grow and flourish. Empowering was named for her excellence in reminding and realizing students that their actions and behavior are not appropriate. Cultural Compassionate received her nickname because she understands and recognizes the unique identities and experiences of each of her students.

Furthermore, Firm Facilitator earned his nickname due to his firmness in maintaining authority and discipline inside the classroom while also facilitating engaging and interactive learning experiences for students. Welcoming was chosen for the participant who provides guidance and support in a warm and inviting manner where students feel embraced and encouraged to freely express themselves without fear of judgement while still managing to maintain boundaries. Adaptive received her nickname due to her flexibility and ability to adapt her teaching methods and language to meet the diverse needs of the students. Empathetic received her nickname for being a compassionate listener and advisor. She prioritized patience in her interactions with students, creating a safe and supportive space for them to express themselves freely. Balanced earned her nickname due to her fairness and thoughtful approach in addressing student behavior, taking into account both the student's perspective and the need for clear boundaries. Guiding Beacon was chosen for the participant, who serves as a source of guidance and a guiding light or example for students to follow in terms of respectful behavior and attitudes towards others. Lastly, Approachable was the pseudonym for another participant because of her ability to make it easy for students to have open communication and have room for expressing their emotions and problems while also maintaining the level of authority and leadership in the classroom.

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>In-Depth Interview (Pseudonyms)</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Years of Teaching</i>	<i>Code</i>
Gentle	28	Male	8 years	IDI-01
Kindhearted	30	Male	7 years	IDI-02
Compassionate Caretaker	28	Female	6 years	IDI-03
Attentive Observer	28	Female	7 years	IDI-04
Nurturing	35	Male	6 years	IDI-05
Empowering	29	Female	6 years	IDI-06
Cultural Compassionate	28	Female	4 years	IDI-07
Firm Facilitator	28	Male	6 years	IDI-08
Welcoming	29	Female	6 years	IDI-09
Adaptive	28	Female	7 years	IDI-10
Empathetic	28	Female	4 years	IDI-11
Balance	28	Female	5 years	IDI-12
Guiding Beacon	30	Male	7 years	IDI-13
Approachable	35	Female	6 years	IDI-14
Total = 14				

All participants answered the same set of questions. The selection of participants was based on their involvement and experiences as college instructors, which were identified by the researcher and verified through personal declarations provided by the participants.

The in-depth interview was conducted face-to-face, as it proved to be more convenient for the participants and facilitated a personal and engaging atmosphere, enabling deeper insights and better interpretation of non-verbal cues. Moreover, immediate clarification and follow-up questions could be made in order to gain a deeper understanding of the experiences of the participants. Most of the participants requested a hard copy of the interview guide, which was provided to them in their respective offices. The researcher accommodated participants' requests to adjust and reschedule interviews in response to unexpected circumstances. Furthermore, the researcher acknowledged the importance of conducting face-to-face interviews in upholding the validity and reliability of the research.

Categorization of Data

After conducting in-depth interviews, the interview responses were transcribed, translated, and analyzed. The analysis commenced with the coding process, which involved organizing the materials into segments of texts to derived meaningful information. Through coding, descriptions of the participant's settings and thematic categories were generated to shape an overall depiction of the phenomenon under study. Date results were presented in the form of table. The data gathered was handed to the data analyst for analysis of data and emerging themes.

The data was categorized into central themes based on the research questions, and these themes were presented. Thorough discussions were conducted to vividly describe the emerged themes from the study, while the core ideas of the participants' responses were also included in the table alongside the major themes.

The second step was the data analysis which settled on as presented in table 2. To categorize the data, the themes were presented according to the research questions and referred to as central themes, while the opposing significant themes were represented as co-ideas from the participants' responses, which served as the basis for classifying them into general, typical and variant categories, as discussed above.

Research Question No. 1: What are the experiences of teachers in their formal correspondence with the students?

To answer this research question, in-depth interviews were conducted with the participants, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked to understand their experiences regarding of the challenges that teachers faced in their formal correspondence with students.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 1 were presented in table 2. From the answers of the participants, six major themes had emerged; having language barriers towards effective communication, crossing the line between teacher and student relationship, extending service beyond the working hours, struggling in the absence of proper etiquette in dealing with teachers, experiencing lack of respect from students, having message misinterpretation in online platform.

Table 2. *Experiences of College Instructors in Their Formal Correspondence with Students*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Having Language Barriers towards Effective Communication	<p>“During the class session, usually the student raises a question, approaches the instructor or somewhat like they have a concern with the subject of the instructor. That is why it is usually difficult for them to raise a concern. Number one reason is, the communication, especially because the English language of communication is implemented in the classroom. Secondly, maybe the students will feel intimidated by the instructor.” – IDI-01</p> <p>“Common or possible problems that I have encountered in student-teacher formal correspondence is the communication barriers. Because we varied from the language it is spoken, from the dialect.” – IDI-07</p> <p>“We are instructed to use English, but it is not applicable to the students because I have tried before to teach a non-board program, and they are struggling. I usually use my mother tongue. If other students are not very good at English and are shy to ask questions, Sometimes, I can see on their faces that they are struggling, and I am the one who asks a question. There and all. They are too shy to ask because of the language used, or they might make a mistake.” – IDI-10</p> <p>“For example, I gave instructions and then I gave the instruction over and over again, there was one student who did not get what the instructions were being given. Maybe, because sometimes I used the English for instruction, sometimes Tagalog.” – IDI- 11</p> <p>“When there are discussions that you really need to discuss properly because you cannot understand whether they understand because they do not speak. In business, it is encouraged to speak English in full but we also have terminologies that are very broad, which will be difficult for the students. Even simple terms will be difficult because we do not speak English inside the classroom, so we have to use Bisaya so students will understand you. Sometimes the answer is out of this world.” – IDI-14</p>
Crossing the Line between Teacher and Student Relationship	<p>“I am aware of the 3rd and 4th year students who are exposed, like regarding the scenario in college in class. But I can always compare them because, usually, when they are new to college, they are different. Very approachable to the instructor, but the connection with the instructor is not that close. But in the 4th year, you are treated differently; the relationship is like being a sibling; that is the treatment. I am now aware that at that level of the student's, their correspondence with their instructor is that casual.” - IDI-01</p> <p>“Another challenge is that sometimes, there is crossing these barriers in which you cannot really avoid even if you create a gap with your students. Because sometimes that familiarity is there. Because we all know that being a teacher is not just about teaching them inside the classroom. Sometimes the gap between the teacher and student really disappears.” – IDI-02</p>

	<p>“They always tease me, and especially during the face-to-face classes, others think that you are just friends. That loses the formality. They forgot that I am also their teacher. So, there are instances where they lose respect.” -IDI-03</p> <p>“The way they interact with me. Let us say, for example, not just in the class but in a situation where, let’s say, outside or in a hallway. Sometimes, the other students, especially the ones who feel that they are close to you, and we really cannot avoid that, there are also students who will get close with you or you will encounter students like that. So, with that, sometimes they forget to recognize you, and sometimes they forget that, at the end of the day, you are still their teacher. But then, I did not take it as a big deal, I guess. For me, it is okay; however, when we are inside the classroom, I am still your teacher.” – IDI-06</p> <p>“Although we have what we call relationships, I hope that it will not go where you are almost siblings or friends.” - IDI-07</p>
<p>Extending Service Beyond the Working Hours</p>	<p>“Sometimes you will also see someone chatting with you late at night, and then that is also one of the indicators I can say. Apparently, there is already a problem because there are no things that, let us say, a student will approach you at any time, which is inappropriate.” – IDI-02</p> <p>“They do not have much respect towards when they ask. They chat in the middle of the night.” – IDI-03</p> <p>“Before, you should really follow to not really disturb your teacher; now, the kids just chat in the middle of the night and give assignments.” – IDI-05</p> <p>“There are some students who would always chat during non-office hours, asking for clarifications about the lesson, especially with those students who are under the research. That is most likely the problem since they are always communicating with their panelists and with their advisers beyond the office hours, which are from 8 a.m. to 5 p.m. Somehow, they are invading most of our time, answering their questions, so we do not have much time with ourselves since knowing that is beyond the office work.” – IDI-08</p> <p>“When they go to text or chat with their instructors in the middle of the night without considering the time of the teacher and instructor, it could mean disrespect to the instructor.” – IDI-13</p>
<p>Struggling in the Absence of Proper Etiquette in Dealing with Teachers</p>	<p>“I am a person who implements when we are at school; this is our level when we are inside the school. but if we are outside, it’s okay with me. So, when I hear something, especially one-on-one, like sir, they go straight to the office or the table, first I feel insulted. Secondly, when respect can’t be revealed or exposed.” – IDI-01</p> <p>“Problems are that despite you or despite us telling them what the proper ways are in order for them to communicate with the instructors, there are still students that they failed to follow, no matter what. An example is if they have concern, so supposedly you have to greet first, good morning or good afternoon, ma’am, and you will now state the concern right now. There are also some students who are waiting for the instructors to reply because all they have to say is good morning, ma’am. So, what am I going to do with the good morning? Another concern is that there are some students who just chat with their friends straight away like this without having to consider greeting first.” – IDI-04</p> <p>“It is challenging in a sense that we cannot please people, especially the students. Although you keep on reminding the students what would be the proper etiquette for that, we cannot enforce that one immediately, and we also cannot force the students to obey. Although they will comply for a particular moment, for the next time around, they can still repeat it. So, we cannot have the assurance for that.” – IDI-06</p> <p>“When they do not know how to greet, like they just passed for specific queries without greeting their teachers, and that is actually informal already.” – IDI-08</p> <p>“For example, the student will chat, so I, my students, always remind them that this is how we are going to construct your message to your instructors. You have to greet them, and next is all the concern. It cannot be a good evening, ma’am, and then wait for the teacher to reply. You should state your concerns for it to be just one click and not time-consuming for the teacher.” – IDI-09</p> <p>“Some of my students honestly tend to use punctuation marks inappropriately. They would be telling me ma’am, with the emoji of like crying. I would be assessing that okay there is something wrong. But when I ask for the detail, it seems like it is just a trip, it’s just char.” – IDI-12</p> <p>“There are cases where students are not so well acquainted with how they approach their instructor. Some just go directly to their instructor and ask questions without greeting their instructors; it could be good day, good morning, or good afternoon, something that will please their instructor or teacher.” – IDI-13</p>
<p>Experiencing Lack of Respect from Students</p>	<p>“There are students who will go straight, or maybe they feel like we are on the same level of age. They just go straight without greeting or saying ma’am.” – IDI-03</p> <p>“The common problems that I encounter when it comes to communicating, especially with my students, are that sometimes there are students who forget to address you properly.” – IDI-06</p> <p>“Inside the classroom, there are some semiotic measures or gestures of our students that are not formal already. Some would have f*ck you and whatsoever, and that is not really; you should not be in the classroom when the teacher is around.” – IDI-08</p> <p>“If they do not say ma’am or sir, we hate that. Of course, I’m already informing them that whoever you’re talking to—the utility, security guard, driver, or vendor—always addresses ma’am and sir with respect.” -IDI-11</p> <p>“They do not take the matter seriously at hand, and as a matter of fact, they do not know how to communicate effectively because respect and ethical consideration in communication are not a matter of how professional the person you are talking with is, but it would matter how professional you are, not because you have the diploma, but because you know how to communicate effectively.” – IDI-12</p> <p>“They are too impolite and make some excuses, especially when they are going to pee or go to the bathroom</p>

Having Message Misinterpretation in Online Platforms

or whatever stuff they are going to do outside the class, and they don't seek permission from me to allow them to go out, so that's one of the challenges that I have experienced. And aside from that, there are cases where these students are not going to ask for permission to enter the class when they are late, so they just immediately get inside, go in their seats, and sit down without seeking or, as they could say, showing their type of politeness and respect by entering the class or by just saying good morning or good afternoon. It is kind of disrespectful on the part of the instructor." – IDI-13

"There are some who have no manners; you will be offended, especially if they are in front of you in class; they answer you; there is no sign of respect." – IDI-14

"That is one thing. For me, it is normal, but for her, he is already angry. The way I talk to them or maybe the way they receive the message, they interpret it differently." – IDI-01

"When it comes to social media, there is a misinterpretation. Yes, social media is a good way to easily connect with each other, but the risk is that you cannot visibly see their intentions, or is it prone to misinterpretation. Unlike face-to-face, you can clarify things." – IDI-02

"I cannot set my tone online. That feeling that you are very angry, but when they receive the chat, it is normal for them." – IDI-07

"There are a lot of factors that we need to consider when we are having our online communication because we could not really hear our students on how they pronounced it or how they were going to deliver it because they just chatted about the things that they wanted to talk about with us." – IDI-08

"Another thing is miscommunication, because your students use inappropriate things like emojis, and it can affect how you interpret the message from your students. And the use of punctuation—it can really add." – IDI-09

"Sometimes, there is a misinterpretation when I do not use an emoji, and maybe when they read it, they think that I am angry or irritated." – IDI-11

"There is always a decrease in formality when it is done online because you will not be able to analyze the pitch of that particular person, the tone, or the emotion during that time. So, there might be particular miscommunication or misinterpretation of the messages possible." – IDI-12

Having Language Barriers towards Effective Communication

The theme highlights the challenges college instructors face due to language barriers, particularly in effective communication. Instructors struggle to communicate effectively with students, often encountering issues that hinder their ability to raise concerns and convey instructions in English. Despite implementing language instruction, many students still have difficulty understanding and using the language, which leads to communication challenges. Their fear of making mistakes further discourages verbal interaction, resulting in shyness or hesitation during class discussions and expression in the target language.

As a result, learners could experience shyness or hesitation when engaging in class discussions or expressing themselves in the target language.

Based on the experiences of Gentle (pseudonym), he highlighted that students often face difficulty raising questions or concerns with their instructor. The language of communication is a major barrier, especially when English is utilized in the classroom. Students find it challenging to fully comprehend the instructor's explanations or to express themselves clearly due to the language being used. Furthermore, he pointed out that intimidation on the part of the teacher can hinder communication. Several factors, including the authority and teaching style of the instructor, may contribute to this intimidation factor. Gentle's (pseudonym) mentioned:

"During the class session, kasagaran gyud noh is ang student is mo raise question, mo approached sa instructor or somewhat like naa silay concern with the subject mismo sa instructor. Mao nay kasagaran nga maglisod silag raise og concern. Number one reason is, the communication, labi na kay implemented sa classroom ang English nga language sa communication. Secondly, is maybe ang students will feel intimidation sa instructor." (IDI-01)

(During the class session, usually the student raises a question, approaches the instructor or somewhat like they have a concern with the subject of the instructor. That is why it is usually difficult for them to raise a concern. Number one reason is, the communication, especially because the English language of communication is implemented in the classroom. Secondly, maybe the students will feel intimidated by the instructor.)

As with the other participant, Cultural Compassionate (pseudonym) shared the common or potential problems she encountered in student-teacher formal correspondence, particularly focusing on communication barriers arising from language differences. She emphasizes that teachers may face difficulties in effectively communicating with the students due to language differences. She shared:

"Common or possible problems na akong na encounter in student-teacher formal correspondence is the communication barriers. Kasi nga we varied from the language it is spoke, from the dialect." (IDI-07)

(Common or possible problems that I have encountered in student-teacher formal correspondence is the communication barriers. Because we varied from the language it is spoken, from the dialect.)

In addition, Adaptive (pseudonym), she illustrated the challenges faced as an instructor in adhering to English instructions. She finds it hard because students have difficulty understanding and are often too shy to ask questions due to the language used. Consequently,

the instructor switches to using their mother tongue to facilitate comprehension but still observes students' hesitation to engage in class discussions. She mentioned:

“Usually, ang gina instruct sa ato is English jud pero dili man siya applicable sa mga students kay naka try man ko before og nag teach kog non-board ma compare nako, maglisod jud sila. Usually, naga gamit lang kog mother tongue nga language. Mag question is English jud na usually. Kung sa uban student kanang dili gyud kaayo hawd mag English and everything maulaw mana sila mangutana. Although, naay usahay kanang makita nako sa ilahang face, ako na lay mu kuan nga naa kay question gang? Ana and all. Mulaw man gyud sila mangutana tungod sa pag use sa language or basig mamali sila.” (IDI-10)

(We are instructed to use English, but it is not applicable to the students because I have tried before to teach a non-board program, and they are struggling. I usually use my mother tongue. If other students are not very good at English and are shy to ask questions, Sometimes, I can see on their faces that they are struggling, and I am the one who asks a question. There and all. They are too shy to ask because of the language used, or they might make a mistake)

Moreover, Empathetic (pseudonym) expressed frustration with a student's inability to understand instructions despite repeated efforts to clarify. Thus, this highlights the challenge of maintaining clear communication in a multilingual classroom setting and underscores the importance of consistent language use to facilitate understanding among all students. She stated:

“For example, nag hatag ko og instructions unya sigi nakog balik-balik og hatag ang instruction naa goy isa ka estudyante nga wala sya naka gets kung unsa ang mga instructions na gina hatag. Siguro, kanang mag hatag ko og instruction kay usahay English, usahay Tagalog.” (IDI-11)

(For example, I gave instructions and then I gave the instruction over and over again, there was one student who did not get what the instructions were being given. Maybe, because sometimes I used the English for instruction, sometimes Tagalog.)

Lastly, Approachable (pseudonym), expressed the challenges of conducting discussions effectively in a business context where English is encouraged but may not be fully understood by all the students. She mentioned the difficulty in conveying complex concepts and terminologies in English, especially when the class predominantly communicates in Bisaya. Thus, this language barrier leads to misunderstandings and makes it challenging for students to grasp even simple terms. In addition, she emphasizes the necessity of using Bisaya to ensure comprehension. She shared:

“Kanang sa discussion na nga need gyud nimo og e discuss og tarong kay dili ka makasabot og nakasabot ba sila kay dili maningog. Sa business, gina encourage jud nga English in full pero naa man gud mi mga terminologies nga grabe ka broad, mag lisod ang estudyante, maglisod man gani baskin simple terms kay dili jud ingon nga English speaking mi inside the classroom so mag Bisaya jud kay aron masabtan ka sa mga estudyante. Usahay dili pa gyud mag tugma mo out of this world kaayo ang tubag.” (IDI-14)

(When there are discussions that you really need to discuss properly because you cannot understand whether they understand because they do not speak. In business, it is encouraged to speak English in full but we also have terminologies that are very broad, it will be difficult for the students, even simple terms will be difficult because we do not speak English inside the classroom, so we have to use Bisaya for students will understand you. Sometimes the answer is out of this world.)

Crossing the Line between Teacher and Student Relationship

The theme discusses the difficult situations that college instructors face when their students behave inappropriately or communicate inappropriately with them. This is often the result of over-familiarity with their teachers and forgetting that they are teachers as well as instructors, treating them more like friends than authoritative figures. This can result in a lack of professionalism, especially when students are interacting with their teachers. Thus, in order to maintain professionalism, respect, and an environment that is favorable to learning in educational settings, college instructors emphasize the significance of upholding clear boundaries in student-teacher relationships.

During the interview, Gentle (pseudonym) expresses an observation regarding the evolving dynamics of student-instructor relationships over the course of student's college years. He notes a distinction between the behavior of first year students compared to those in their third and fourth years. Initially, first year students are approachable but maintain a more formal relationship with their instructors. However, by the time they reach their fourth year, there is a noticeable shift in the relationship, resembling that of siblings. He highlights that at this stage, students interact with instructors in a more casual and familiar manner, indicating a deeper level of connection and comfort. Gentle (pseudonym) mentioned:

“Aware ko sa mga 3rd year and 4th year nga sanay, exposed na like regarding sa scenario sa college nga diay sa klase always ma compare man nako kay usually, pag bag-ohan pa sa college, medyo dili pa ing-ana sila ka approach kaayo sa instructor like, connection sa instructor dili ing-ana ka close. Pag 4th year naman gud, lahi na inyohang treatment, mura ba'g ang relationship mura nalang og mag igsuon noh, ing-ana ang treatment. Dira ko na aware nga pag ing-ana na ang level sa studyante, is ang ilahang correspondence sa ilang instructor, ing-ana na ka casual.” (IDI-01)

(I am aware of the 3rd and 4th year students that they are exposed, like regarding the scenario in college. But I can always compare them because, usually, when they are new to college, they are different. Very approachable to the instructor, but the connection with

the instructor is not that close. But in the 4th year, you are treated differently; the relationship is like being a sibling; that is the treatment. I am now aware that at that level of the student's, their correspondence with their instructor is that casual.)

In addition to Kindhearted (pseudonym), experience revolves around the challenge of maintaining boundaries between teachers and students, particularly when familiarity develops over time. Despite efforts to establish a professional distance, he acknowledges that closeness can naturally occur due to the nature of teaching, which extends beyond the confines of the classroom. As he mentioned the closeness can really blur the boundaries between teacher and student, making it challenging to maintain a strictly formal relationship. He stated:

“Another challenge siguro is sometimes, there is crossing these barriers in which hindi talaga maiwasan kahit you create a gap with your students. Kasi sometimes nandoon yong familiarity minsan. Kasi we all know that being a teacher is not just about teaching them inside the classroom. Minsan yung gap between the teacher and student minsan nawawala talaga.” (IDI-02)

(Another challenge is that sometimes, there is crossing these barriers in which you cannot really avoid even if you create a gap with your students. Because sometimes that familiarity is there. Because we all know that being a teacher is not just about teaching them inside the classroom. Sometimes the gap between the teacher and student really disappears.)

Moreover, Compassionate Caretaker (pseudonym) experienced challenges related to maintaining professional boundaries and respect from students. She added instances where students demonstrate a lack of respect, likely coming from the perception of friendship rather than a teacher-student dynamic. She shared:

“Sigi silag pangulit sa akua and especially pud, during sa face-to-face classes, magtuo ang uban na barkada ra kaayo mo. Kanang mawala gani ang formality nga ay teacher man diay nako ni. So, naay mga instances gyud nga kanang mawad-an silag respeto.” (IDI-03)

(They always tease me, and especially during the face-to-face classes, others think that you are just friends. That loses the formality. They forgot that I am also their teacher. So, there are instances where they lose respect.)

Additionally, Empowering (pseudonym) expressed the way students interact with her, particularly outside of the classroom environment. She highlights situations where students become overly familiar with her, which leads to blurring the boundaries between her as a teacher and friend. Despite efforts to maintain professionalism, some students forget to recognize her role as their teacher. However, she mentioned that she does not view this behavior as a significant issue. Nevertheless, she emphasizes that inside the classroom, they still expect to be respected as the teacher. She mentioned:

“The way they interact with me. Let say, for example not just in the class but in a situation where in ano lang siya, let say, for example sa gawas or hallway. Sometimes, ang uban man gud nga mga students, kana ganing most especially yung mga feel na kayo nga close na imoha and dili pud na siya maiwasan nga naa pud jud kay ma close or ma encounter na mga students. So, with that, usahay malimtan na nila ang pag recognize sa imoha, usahay malimtan na nga at the end of the day, teacher diay gihapon ka nila. But then, I did not ano kumbaga wala nako na siya gi take as kana ganing gi big deal, kumbaga. For me naman, it's okay naman, however pag naa ta sa sulod sa classroom, still, teacher gihapon ko nimo.” (IDI-06)

(The way they interact with me. Let us say, for example, not just in the class but in a situation where, let us say, outside or in a hallway. Sometimes, the other students, especially the ones who feel that they are close to you, and we really cannot avoid that, there are also students who will get close with you or you will encounter students like that. So, with that, sometimes they forget to recognize you, and sometimes they forget that, at the end of the day, you are still their teacher. But then, I did not take it as a big deal, I guess. For me, it is okay; however, when we are inside the classroom, I am still your teacher.)

Lastly, Cultural Compassionate (pseudonym) expresses a desire to maintain boundaries in relationships with students, emphasizing the importance of professionalism and avoiding becoming overly familiar. She explained that while relationships with students exist, she hopes they do not evolve to the point where the dynamic resembles that of siblings or friends. But rather, preserving a clear distinction between the roles of teacher and student, prioritizing professionalism, and maintaining appropriate boundaries within the educational context. She said:

“Although naa tay ginatawag na kanang relationship pero dili unta siya halos murag igsuon nalang mo or unsa ba or kanang barkada.” (IDI-07)

(Although we have what we call relationships, I hope that it will not go where you are almost siblings or friends.)

Extending Service Beyond the Working Hours

The theme focuses on the difficulties college instructors encounter when students engage in informal interaction, such as messaging late at night, and how this conduct affects the boundaries between teachers and students. Students who communicate with teachers informally or at inappropriate times can be interpreted as disrespecting professional boundaries and could put excessive pressure on teachers to respond to messages beyond their regular office hours. Teachers may find it difficult to maintain a work-life balance as a result of this behavior because they feel obligated to respond to student inquiries right away.

During the interview, Kindhearted (pseudonym) expressed concern about students contacting him late at night, which he perceived as inappropriate. He also mentioned that such behavior indicates a problem with boundaries, as students may feel entitled to approach the teacher at any time, regardless of the appropriateness of the hour. He highlights the value of clear boundaries between teacher and student interactions and recognizes that students contacting him at late hours can disrupt personal time and boundaries. Kindhearted (pseudonym) stated:

“Minsan makikita mo din doon na may mag chachat sayo late night and then yon isa na din yon sa masasabi ko na indicators. Kumbaga, there is already a problem kasi wala namang mga bagay na let say as student will approach you any time which is inappropriate.” (IDI-02)

(Sometimes you will also see someone chatting with you late at night, and then that is also one of the indicators I can say. Apparently, there is already a problem because there are no things that, let's say, a student will approach you at any time, which is inappropriate.)

As with the other participant, Compassionate Caretaker's (pseudonym) experience, she expressing frustration with students' lack of respect and inappropriate behavior, specifically their tendency to chat with her in the middle of the night. This experience suggests that students may not fully understand or respect boundaries regarding when it is appropriate to communicate with their teacher. She mentioned:

“Wala gyud kaayo silay tahod towards pag mangutana sila. Mag sigi silag chat tungag gabie mag sig chat.” (IDI-03)

“They do not have much respect towards when they ask. They chat in the middle of the night.”

Moreover, Nurturing (pseudonym) expressed his experiences of a shift in student behavior over time. He mentioned that, they describe a previous era where students were expected to be considerate and not disturb their teacher unnecessarily. However, contemporary students now engage in chatting in the middle of the night. He believed that this shift suggests a lack of awareness or disregard for boundaries between students and teachers, as well as a blurring of roles where students may assume a level of familiarity and authority that was previously uncommon. He stated:

“Kadtong kuan gud sa una nga e ano gyud nimo ang teacher nga dili gyud nimo disturbohon tungang gabie, nah karon mo chat lang gihapon ang bata tungang gabie mag pasa og mga assignments. Isa, isa na siya sa mga kuan.” (IDI-05)

(Before, you should really follow to not really disturb your teacher; now, the kids just chat in the middle of the night and give assignments.)

Furthermore, Firm Facilitator (pseudonym) expressed her feelings about students who frequently contact them outside of office hours, particularly those involved in research who communicate with their panelists and advisors beyond designated times. This behavior consumes a significant portion of the teacher's time, leaving little opportunity for personal time or other responsibilities. Firm Facilitator (pseudonym) highlights the challenge of maintaining work-life balance when students invade non-office hours for clarifications and assistance, indicating the need for clear boundaries and communication protocols. He mentioned:

“There are some students who would always chat during non-office hours, asking for clarifications about the lesson, especially with those students who are under the research. That is most likely the problem since they are always communicating with their panelists and with their advisers beyond the office hours, which are from 8 a.m. to 5 p.m. Somehow, they are invading most of our time answering their questions, so we don't have much time with ourselves since knowing that is beyond the office work.” (IDI-08)

Lastly, Guiding Beacon (pseudonym) stated that it is a concern about students contacting their instructors late at night without considering the teacher's time. He interpreted this behavior as disrespectful towards the instructor. This experience from Guiding Beacon (pseudonym) pertains to valuing and respecting boundaries regarding appropriate times for communication. It highlights the importance of students being mindful of their instructors' schedules and personal time. He said:

“When they go to text or chat with their instructors in the middle of the night without considering the time of the teacher and instructor, it could mean disrespect to the instructor.” (IDI-13)

Struggling in the Absence of Proper Etiquette in Dealing with Teachers

The theme explores the challenges faced by college instructors due to a lack of formal etiquette among their students when communicating or interacting with them. Despite instructor's instructions to maintain a certain level of formality, students struggle with basic etiquette such as greetings when addressing their teachers. This absence of proper etiquette in communication creates difficulties for instructors, leading to a breakdown in respectful communication and potentially hindering effective teacher-student relationships. Furthermore, the theme underscores the importance of etiquette in fostering respectful and productive interactions between students and teachers.

Based on the experience of Gentle (pseudonym) challenging experiences revolve around differences in behavior inside and outside of school contexts. He mentioned that while he is comfortable with informal interactions outside of school, he expects a certain level of formality and respect when students address him within the school environment. However, when students approach him informally or disrespectfully, such as by addressing him directly by his name without proper protocol or approaching his office or table casually,

Gentle (pseudonym) feels insulted and disrespected. Gentle (pseudonym) mentioned:

“Ako gyud na tao, I implement pag naa ko sa school ing-ana ang atoang level noh sa school kay naa man jud gina practice noh as kanang educator. Pag sa gawas, okay ra sa akoo nan noh. So, kani man gud pag naa koy madunggan labi na sa one-on-one, like sir muadto sila sa opisina or sa table diritso noh, mao jud na akoang first na ma feel, ma insulto. Secondly, uhm dili mapadayag or dili ma exposed ang respect gyud.” (IDI-01)

(I am a person who implements when we are at school; this is our level when we are inside the school. but if we are outside, it is okay with me. So, when I hear something, especially one-on-one, like sir, they go straight to the office or the table, first I feel insulted. Secondly, when respect cannot be revealed or exposed.)

Additionally, Attentive Observer (pseudonym) highlights challenges regarding student’s failure to adhere to proper communication etiquette with instructors despite being instructed on the correct protocols. She mentioned that some students neglect to greet their instructors properly before expressing their concerns, while others simply send a greeting without stating their purpose. Thus, these experiences illustrate the difficulty instructors face in encouraging students to follow communication norms and the importance of reinforcing these expectations for effective teacher-student interactions. She stated:

“Problems are despite you or despite us telling them unsa man tong mga proper ways in order for them to communicate the instructors, naa gyud gihapon mga students na they failed to follow, kung unsa man to. Example nalang ana is, if they have concern. Naa man gud uban students na muhulat pa og kanos-a mureply ang instructors kay ang ilaha lang isulti is good morning, ma’am. So, what am I going to do with the good morning? Another, concern na naman is naa puy uban nga mga estudyante na mura ra’g ni chat og mga barkada nga diritso lang pud nga ma’am without having to consider ba nga, oy naka limot ko nga dapat e greet diay nako siya dapat.” (IDI-04)

(Problems are that despite you or despite us telling them what the proper ways are in order for them to communicate with the instructors, there are still students that they failed to follow, no matter what. An example is if they have concern, so supposedly you have to greet first, good morning or good afternoon, ma’am, and you will now state the concern right now. There are also some students who will just wait for the instructors to reply before expressing their concern. So, what am I going to do with the good morning? Another concern is that there are some students who will chat as if I am their friend without having to consider greeting first.)

As with the other participants, Empowering (pseudonym) expressed the challenges of maintaining proper communication etiquette among students despite consistent reminders. Though she acknowledged the difficulty in immediately instilling these norms and the inability to force students to consistently adhere to them, even if students comply momentarily, there is no guarantee they will continue to do so in the future. This lack of assurance creates ongoing challenges for her in ensuring that students communicate respectfully and appropriately. He shared:

“Very challenging siya in a sense na nga dili man nato ma please noh ang tao most especially ang students. Though, you keep on reminding the students what would be the proper etiquette for that however, we cannot enclose that one immediately and dili pud nato mapugos ang mga students nga tumanon na siya. Though tumanon na nila for a particular moment, but then, for the next time around, pwede ra gihapon na nila balikon. So, we cannot have the assurance for that.” (IDI-06)

(It is challenging in a sense that we cannot please people, especially the students. Although you keep on reminding the students what would be the proper etiquette for that, we cannot enclose that one immediately, and we also cannot force the students to obey. Although they will comply for a particular moment, for the next time around, they can still repeat it. So, we cannot have the assurance for that.)

Moreover, Firm Facilitator (pseudonym) expressed the issue of students failing to greet their teachers properly before asking specific queries, considering it as an informal behavior. This observation highlights a lack of adherence to expected communication etiquette within the student-teacher relationship. Firm Facilitator (pseudonym) suggests that a proper greeting is necessary before addressing teachers with queries to maintain formality and respect. He mentioned:

“When they do not know how to greet, like they just passed for specific queries without greeting their teachers and that is actually informal already.” - IDI-08)

Consequently, based on Welcoming (pseudonym), she expresses the importance of teaching students how to construct their messages to instructors effectively. She emphasizes the importance of including a greeting followed by stating their concerns in one message rather than merely offering a greeting and waiting for the teacher to respond before stating their concerns. She mentioned:

“For example, mag chat ang estudyante, so ako, sa mga students nako I always remind them nga this is how we are going to construct your message to your instructors. You have to greet them and next is maisa ra tanan ang concern. Dili pwede nga good evening, ma’am niya mureply si ma’am, didto pa pud ka muingon sa imong concern. Dapat isahon ra nimo para sa pag click sa instructor is maisa ra tanan imong concern para dili kaayo siya ing-ana ka time consuming.” (IDI-09)

(For example, the student will chat, so I, to my students, always remind them that this is how we are going to construct your message to your instructors. You have to greet them, and next is all the concern. It cannot be a good evening, ma’am, and then wait for the teacher to reply. You should state your concerns for it to be just one click and not time-consuming for the teacher.)

On the other hand, Balance (pseudonym) expressed some student's inappropriate use of punctuation marks, particularly in online communication. She gives an example where a student uses an emoji indicating distress, leading her to believe that something is wrong. However, upon further inquiry, it becomes clear that the student's message was not serious but rather playful or lighthearted ("just a trip, just char"). This experience highlights the challenge of interpreting tone and intention in digital communication, where punctuation and emojis can be misinterpreted. Balance's (pseudonym) statement emphasizes the significance of precise and clear communication, along with the necessity for students to employ suitable punctuation to properly communicate their ideas. She shared:

"Some of my students honestly tend to use punctuation mark inappropriately. They would be telling me ma'am, with the emoji of like crying. I would be assessing na ah okay there is something wrong. But when I ask for the detail, kay murag trip lang, char lang daw." (IDI-12)

(Some of my students honestly tend to use punctuation marks inappropriately. They would be telling me ma'am, with the emoji of like crying. I would be assessing that okay there is something wrong. But when I ask for the detail, it seems like it is just a trip, it is just char.)

Lastly, Guiding Beacon (pseudonym) shares his experiences and observations regarding how some students do not know how to appropriately approach their teachers. He brought up incidents in which students addressed their teachers immediately and asked inquiries without saying good morning. This observation highlights the value of teaching student's appropriate classroom behavior, including the importance of acknowledging and respecting their teachers before starting a conversation. He pointed out:

"There are cases where students are not so well acquainted with how they approach their instructor. Some just go directly to their instructor and ask questions without greeting their instructors; it could be good day, good morning, or good afternoon, something that will please their instructor or teacher." (IDI-13)

Experiencing Lack of Respect from Students

The theme addresses the challenges faced by college instructors due to students' inability to communicate effectively with respect and their impolite behavior. Teachers often encounter situations in which students act impolitely, such as not excusing themselves when they leave the classroom to use the restroom or making improper semiotic gestures. Moreover, the theme highlights the need for teachers to address and correct disrespectful behavior to ensure mutual respect and professionalism in the student-teacher relationship.

Based on the experience of Compassionate Caretaker (pseudonym), she expressed the challenges related to respect and acknowledgement from some students, as they may not greet her or acknowledge her authority. Based on her experience, she perceives a disconnect in the way some students look at her, possibly feeling that they see her as their peer rather than an authority figure. Compassionate (pseudonym) said:

"During mag klase ko usahay naa koy kanang ma ingnan kay dili na siya mag ma'am mudiritso or siguro ka level lang mi og edad. Mudiritso nalang siya, mao ng muingon nalang ko og ma'am." (IDI-03)

(There are students who will go straight, or maybe they feel like we are on the same level of age. They just go straight without greeting or saying ma'am.)

Additionally, Empowering (pseudonym) expressed what she feels, particularly when the students fail to address her properly. This could indicate a lack of respect or attentiveness from the students, which can hinder effective communication and mutual understanding in the learning environment. She may feel disrespected or undervalued when her students fail to use appropriate forms of address, such as addressing them by their title or name. She stated:

"The common problems that I encounter when it comes to most especially in communicating towards my students sometimes there are students who forget to address you properly." - IDI-06

Furthermore, Firm Facilitator (pseudonym) expresses frustration, disappointment, and a sense of urgency to address inappropriate behavior in the classroom. The use of disrespectful gestures by students is seen as unacceptable and disruptive to the learning environment. He mentioned:

*"Inside the classroom, there are some semiotic measures or gestures of our students that are not formal already. Some would have f*ck you and whatsoever, and that is not really; you should not be in the classroom when the teacher is around."* (IDI-08)

Moreover, Empathetic (pseudonym) expresses her experience with a strong emphasis on respect and etiquette within interactions, particularly in the context of addressing someone, not only those who have authority. The use of "ma'am" or "sir" is viewed as a fundamental display of respect, and the absence of these terms is deemed unacceptable. Empathetic (pseudonym) likely feels a sense of disappointment when encountering individuals who do not adhere to this expectation, as it reflects a disregard for established social norms. She stated:

"Ano especially pag dili mag ma'am or sir hate jud namo na. Syempre gina orient jud nako na sila nga kung kinsa man na inyong kasugat ma utility, ma security guard, ma driver, ma vendor always addressed ma'am and sir, always respect." (IDI-11)

(Especially if they do not say ma'am or sir, we hate that. Of course, I am already informing them that whoever you are talking to—the utility, security guard, driver, or vendor—always addresses ma'am and sir with respect)

On the other hand, Balance (pseudonym) expressed concern regarding the lack of seriousness and professionalism in communication among certain individuals. She emphasized the importance of respect and ethical considerations in communication, highlighting that professionalism is not solely determined by one's qualifications or credentials, but rather by their ability to communicate effectively and respectfully. Balance (pseudonym) highlights the importance of respect and ethical conduct in interactions, regardless of their professional background or status. She said:

“They do not take matter seriously at hand and as a matter of fact, they don't know to communicate effectively because respect and ethical consideration in communication is not a matter of how professional the person you are talking with but it would matter on how professional you are not because you have the diploma but you know how to communicate effectively.” (IDI-12)

In addition, Guiding Beacon (pseudonym) expressed challenges related to student's lack of politeness and respect in the classroom. He specifically mentioned instances where students fail to seek permission before leaving the classroom, such as to use the restroom, and also when entering the classroom late without acknowledging their presence or greeting the instructor. Guiding Beacon (pseudonym) likely emphasizes the importance of basic courtesy and manners in maintaining a respectful learning environment. He stated:

“They are too impolite and make some excuses, especially when they are going to pee or go to the bathroom or whatever stuff they are going to do outside the class, and they do not seek permission from me to allow them to go out, so that is one of the challenges that I have experienced. And aside from that, there are cases where these students are not going to ask for permission to enter the class when they are late, they just immediately get inside, go in their seats, and sit down without seeking or, as they could say, showing their type of politeness and respect by entering the class or by just saying good morning or good afternoon. It is kind of disrespectful on the part of the instructor.” (IDI-13)

Lastly, based on the experience of Approachable (pseudonym), she stresses the lack of respect and manners of certain students, particularly in a classroom setting. Approachable (pseudonym) suggests that this behavior can be offensive, especially when students respond without showing any sign of respect. The emphasis is on the importance of respectful communication and behavior, particularly when interacting with authority figures such as teachers. She shared:

“Naa gyud uban nga walay batasan ma-offend gyud ka noh labi na og naa atobangan sa klase mutubag sa imo, wala lang may sign of respect.” (IDI-14)

(There are some who have no manners; you will be offended, especially if they are in front of you in class; they answer you; there is no sign of respect.)

Having Message Misinterpretation in Online Platforms

The theme revolves around the challenges the college instructors encountered when utilizing digital media for communication, as it is prone to misinterpretation driven by various factors like a lack of non-verbal cues, tone ambiguity, and the use of punctuation marks and emojis. Furthermore, this theme explores how misinterpretations can lead to misunderstandings, conflicts, or even damaged relationships and emphasizes the importance of clarity, analyzing the message, and active listening in continuous communication.

Based on the experience of Gentle (pseudonym) he highlights the subjective nature of communication and the potential for messages to be interpreted differently by different individuals. He expressed an awareness that their manner of speaking or the tone of their message may be perceived differently by others, even when they themselves perceive it as normal or neutral. Gentle (pseudonym) likely emphasizes the importance of considering how messages are received and interpreted by others, acknowledging that individuals may have different sensitivities, perspectives that influence their understanding. Gentle (pseudonym) stated:

“Isa pud na, sa akona normal lang to sa iyaha kay nasuko na lagi si sir, ing-ana ba, lain lagi. The way is different, the way I talk to them or maybe the way they received the message, lahi ilahang pag interpret kumbaga.” (IDI-01)

(That is one thing. For me, it is normal, but for her, he is already angry. The way I talk to them, or maybe the way they receive the message, they interpret it differently.)

Additionally, Kindhearted (pseudonym) expressed concern about the potential for misinterpretation in communication via social media platforms. He highlighted the limitations of digital communication, noting that unlike face-to-face interactions where non-verbal cues and tone can help clarify intentions, social media lacks these cues, making it prone to misinterpretation. He stated:

“Pag social media kasi may misinterpretation. Yes, social media is a good way to easily connect with each other but yung risk naman tendency is you cannot see visibly don sa kanilang let say intention, or yun bang prone to misinterpretation kumbaga. Unlike sa face-to-face, you can clarify things.” (IDI-02)

(When it comes to social media, there is a misinterpretation. Yes, social media is a good way to easily connect with each other, but the risk is that you cannot visibly see their intentions, or that it is prone to misinterpretation. Unlike face-to-face, you can clarify things.)

Moreover, Cultural Compassionate (pseudonym) mentioned the challenge of not being able to convey tone effectively in online communication. He expressed frustration with the limitations of chat platforms, where it is difficult to accurately convey emotions such as anger or frustration through text alone. Cultural Compassionate (pseudonym) experiences the difficulty of having their intended tone misinterpreted by recipients, leading to misunderstandings or confusion. She shared:

“Dili nako ma set ang akoang tone sa online. Kanang feeling nimo suko na kaayo ka pero pag received nila sa chat kay normal ra to sa ilaha.” (IDI-07)

(I cannot set my tone online. That feeling that you are very angry, but when they receive the chat, it is normal for them.)

Consequently, Firm Facilitator (pseudonym) expressed an understanding of the complexities involved in online communication, particularly in educational settings. He highlights the challenges that arise from the inability to hear students' pronunciation and delivery when communicating solely through chat platforms. He pointed:

“There are some a lot of factors that we need to consider when we are having our online communication because we could not really hear our students on how they pronounced it, how they are going to deliver it because they just chatted add with the things that they wanted to talk to us.” (IDI-08)

(There are a lot of factors that we need to consider when we are having our online communication because we could not really hear our students on how they pronounced it or how they were going to deliver it because they just chatted about the things that they wanted to talk about with us.)

Furthermore, Welcoming (pseudonym) expressed difficulty interpreting messages from students due to the use of emojis that may convey unintended emotions or tone. Additionally, she finds that the lack of proper punctuation in messages adds to the challenge of understanding the intended meaning. These challenges can lead to misunderstandings and affect the effectiveness of communication between her students. She stated:

“Another ano gyud ana si miscommunication ba noh labi nag imohang estudyante mag gamit og dili proper like mga emojis and maka add siya og as how you are going to ano the message from your students, isa na sya. And the use of punctuations, ingon ana noh maka add jud na siya.” (IDI-09)

(Another thing is miscommunication, because your students use inappropriate things like emojis, and it can affect how you interpret the message from your students. And the use of punctuation—it can really add.)

In the same way, Empathetic (pseudonym) mentioned instances where not using emojis can lead to misunderstandings, with recipients possibly perceiving their messages as conveying anger or irritation when that is not the intended tone. Empathetic (pseudonym) feel a sense of responsibility to ensure that their messages are accurately understood and received positively by others. This highlights awareness of the importance of non-verbal cues, such as emojis, in conveying emotions and maintaining a friendly tone in digital interactions. She shared:

“Sometimes, naay misinterpretation mahitabo pag kung dili ko mugamit og emoji niya basi sa ilang pagbasa ba nasuko na ba ni si ma'am or nairita ba ni si ma'am.” (IDI-11)

(Sometimes, there is a misinterpretation when I do not use an emoji, and maybe when they read it, they think that I am angry or irritated.)

Lastly, from the interview, Balance (pseudonym) expressed the challenges and potential drawbacks of online communication, particularly in terms of decreased formality and the absence of non-verbal cues such as pitch, tone, and emotion. Balance (pseudonym) highlights that the lack of these cues in online interactions can lead to miscommunications or misinterpretations of messages. She mentioned:

“There would be always a decrease of the formality when it is done online because you will not be able to analyze how it was the pitch of that particular person, the tone, the emotion during that time. So, there might be particular miscommunication or misinterpretation of the messages possible.” (IDI-12)

Research Question No. 2: How do the teacher's cope with the challenges in their formal correspondence with the students?

To answer this research question, in-depth interviews were conducted with the participants, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked about their strategies for coping with the challenges they faced about the ineffective formal communication between students and teachers and how to overcome such barriers. It was revealed that they employ a range of strategies and techniques to solve and overcome these challenges and difficulties.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 2 were presented in Table 3. From the answers of the participants, seven major themes emerged: setting clear expectations at the beginning of a course or program, correcting improper behavior immediately, establishing boundaries and authority in the class, building good rapport through a supportive teacher-student relationship, having an understanding of the various underlying reasons for students' misbehaviors, implementing a policy of language used inside the

classroom, and strengthening student-teacher communication through comprehensive feedback.

Table 3. *Coping Mechanisms for the Challenges Faced by the College Instructors in Their Formal Correspondence with the Students*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Setting Clear Expectations at the Beginning of a Course or Program	<p>"I really imposed formal behavior and personalities that are discussed with them before my subject starts. It is like the information for the entire semester; that is what I always include in the organization." – IDI-01</p> <p>"From the start, I made things clear to them. I see to it that I only cater to concerns relating to academia. In terms of personal, sometimes I just listen, and I try to channel them to the right person who can help them." – IDI-02</p> <p>"Clear communication. Ensuring that my instruction and expectations are communicated effectively towards the students." – IDI-07</p> <p>"My technique and strategy are that you really need to establish rules and regulations for each set of semesters. You need to establish authority with your students, you know. During your class, what are the things that your students need to do." – IDI-08</p> <p>"Establishing a routine or a particular flow of the conversation. Before we would start, I would always give something somewhat like an orientation to that particular student, but it is not that formal. It is quite like orienting the student before we deal with the concern so that I can establish a flow of communication." – IDI-12</p> <p>"At the very beginning of the class, I already gave them the orientation; I am always their instructor, and I already set the boundary that they are my students and I am their teacher. To maintain that kind of standard and boundary, I have a set of rules in my class that they need to follow, and if a particular rule is violated, it means there is a kind of behavior or misbehavior that particular student is showing." – IDI-13</p> <p>"I also set rules, or house rules. You set it up so that you can lay the guards on them so that they know what to expect from your class." – IDI-14</p>
Correcting Improper Behavior Immediately	<p>"What I usually do is call the attention of the student. I call them one-on-one so that I can brief them, talk to them, guide them, and tell them that this is what you should do next time, which he will not get offended by because his classmate did not know." IDI-01</p> <p>"One way to cope is to tell the student personally that there is already a problem, to correct her or him in a sense." – IDI-02</p> <p>"I am going to call him right away. I will talk to them privately to tell them that I don't like your reactions. You are raising your voice a bit. And that is it; I talk to them privately." – IDI-03</p> <p>"I always get the attention of the students. At that time, the student seemed to have forgotten. Dong, you seem to be different now. Good morning, Dong. I will say good morning to him instead of him saying good morning to me. It is like there is a reverse psychology directly that I'm doing to him or them." – IDI-05</p> <p>"The technique that I used was confronting the students immediately." – IDI-06</p> <p>"I do not want that student to not be aware of their actions, and that is why I always call their attention. I always correct them every time they take the wrong action or misbehave. So, those are my techniques." – IDI-13</p> <p>"You have to call the attention of the students. You will tell them personally. You will talk to them so that they will be able to know." – IDI-14</p>
Establishing Boundaries and Authority in the Class	<p>"Before you enter the classroom, it should be clear to them. I am the student, and you are a teacher. There is just an adjustment in how you handle them so far. I always look back at myself to figure out if there are things that I need to change or improve to improve the so-called student-teacher relationship." – IDI-02</p> <p>"You really have to stand up because you cannot be on the same level as your student. Outside, I am okay with bonding with them, but inside, I'm very strict. For me, there should be boundaries between both parties." – IDI-03</p> <p>"As much as possible, when talking to the students, if they have any concerns, that is the only thing I can talk about. If there are instances where the student has gone away from the topic or wants to discuss something that is not part of the concern, I do not entertain it right away. Although I will acknowledge the concern, I have to remind the student that it is not part of the concern, or whatever the reason is, or that I will call or talk to him just to be clear. Because someone is too comfortable with us, we always entertain their thoughts even though they are no longer involved in any concern, so now we are deviating from our purpose, and at the same time we are losing our boundaries." – IDI-04</p> <p>"I really separate. I have a separation between teacher and student. I am the one who maintains that you are my students here inside and that I am your friend outside. So, you have to respect me when we are here at school. Because when we are out, we are friends. Because there are some students who are friends outside, they will bring it inside the school. I have my boundaries; I have to maintain that this is my role here in the office and in what kind of teacher I am." – IDI-05</p> <p>"It is up to the teacher to establish authority inside the class because if your students observe that the teacher doesn't care about what you are doing, then the level of formality inside the classroom will be low. But if you are really highly authoritative inside the classroom, then the level of formality will be high. Meaning, your students are cooperating with you, and they are listening to you as well." – IDI-08</p> <p>"To maintain the professional boundary, do not go beyond topics that are outside of your purpose. If you are an instructor, of course you have to deal with questions about academics. What if your student asks? Of</p>

	<p>course, do not answer a question that you know is beyond the scope of what you are teaching. That's it. Let us just focus on what your purpose is and what is the purpose of that when your student communicates.” – IDI-09</p> <p>“Usually, when I talk to my students or have our class like this, I do not really disclose much to my students, so it seems like I still maintain the boundary. They don't know much about my personal space. More likely, during my classes, I usually set an example for those who meet my students, not about me.” – IDI-10</p> <p>“Keep reminding them that you are students, and if a teacher, address formality. But if we are outside, we know each other. But here in the classroom, I am your teacher, and don't act improperly.” – IDI-11</p> <p>“Make it clear, like setting clear boundaries with the students, that this is how you should respond or that the concerns should be related to the academic topic, not personal or inappropriate questions. That is just to maintain and manage professional boundaries.” – IDI-4</p>
<p>Building Good Rapport through a Supportive Teacher-Student Relationship</p>	<p>“For me to overcome these challenges, I make friends with them. Outside, they can call me their friend, and at least if we are inside, I am their instructor, so they need to respect me.” – IDI-03</p> <p>“Strategies because they have different characteristics and different places where they come from. Especially those children today who come from far away have problem at home, so I also need to adjust, and even for me personally, for my students, I always keep in mind that maybe this child has a problem. So, I reevaluate and ask the other person what the problem is and why. And for me to know. So, I need to take it slowly, even though I am already angry.” – IDI-05</p> <p>“Effective formal communication between the teacher and student eventually leads to frustration and misunderstanding on both sides. And what are my actions or techniques to improve this is to encourage participation among students, and aside from that, number one is to listen to their constraints, and then not only the teacher-students, because the information and learning are coming purely from the teacher, both students and teachers.” – IDI-07</p> <p>“You will make friends with them so that they can feel that they have a comfort zone and that it is okay because there are some who are not open to their family and to their friends. There is a certain person with whom we feel our hearts light and with whom we can communicate better.” – IDI-14</p>
<p>Having an Understanding on the Various Underlying Reasons of Students' Misbehaviors</p>	<p>“My coping mechanism is that there are also understandings. I told them whatever their behavior is at home, they should not bring it to school.” – IDI-03</p> <p>“There must be patience because, of course, we cannot, or we, as the instructor, cannot act if we spot mistakes and get angry and scold right away. So, we have to understand first: why, where did the child come from, and why he is like this? Maybe because that student is not used to it when it comes to formal communication.” – IDI-04</p> <p>“I am slowly adjusting because I need to look at the child. There are students who have different experiences and problems. So, I need to deepen and widen my emotions, even when you are angry. Just be careful when dealing with people, especially those who have different environments.” – IDI-05</p> <p>“It is the same thing with me; they think I am angry, but I am not. So, I will also ask. I will not immediately react to the reaction or his response to me. I asked if he was angry, and they also explained that he was not.” – IDI-11</p> <p>“I would say that I will always have the principle of consideration. In some cases, if I find the concern or if I find the student going beyond the boundary that I have said, I will not always approach him or her in an aggressive manner but rather consider the possible scenario or possible feeling or emotion of that particular student at that time, so I will be able to adjust my response or reaction to his or her actions or to the words that have been used.” – IDI-12</p>
<p>Implementing a Policy of Language Used Inside the Classroom</p>	<p>“I try to ask them questions: Why are you misbehaving and why are you showing those actions? I ask questions so that I can really confirm if that student is misbehaving or not.” – IDI-13</p> <p>“You also need to be sensitive to them because they have different backgrounds and different upbringings. There are other people who are just talking to you but look like they are shouting at you. so, situations like that. You really have different strategies for handling them because they are different.” – IDI-14</p> <p>“Classroom implementation policies. Unlike in the classroom, we only follow the language that we use. Stick to the English language that we will use as long as we are in the classroom, and even for any activities, instructions, everything, deliberations, and discussions, as long as we are in the classroom, we speak English. Aside from that, I do not allow it; I discourage it. But sometimes I allow such cases if they need to apply. For example, Tagalog, because they are having a hard time. I will allow it to use Taglish other than those languages, or whatever they use that they know. I only allow them to use Taglish when we have an activity that needs to be included in the presentation; if it is not applicable, I do not allow it. It should be specified in my communication rules and policies that our language will be used differently. You can only use it if it is applicable to our situation.” – IDI-01</p> <p>“I am teaching English major students, and that is why it is really a prerequisite for them to use the English language. They do not have any other choice because they are the future practitioners of the English language. Maybe this is the perfect time for them to practice their English language during our discussion. But there are times when I can really see if the students are struggling, but I can sense that he has an idea, so now is the time to allow my students to code switch but not totally speak Bisaya. Only code mixing and code switching.” – IDI-08</p> <p>“We usually use English because, even if the student is diverse, it seems like everyone can understand</p>

Strengthening Student-Teacher Communication through Comprehensive Feedback

English or Bisaya. and we use it as our medium of instruction. If they cannot or they find it difficult, we can put more emphasis on the announcement or what you want to inform your students. You use Bisaya so that you can deal with the diversity of the students.” – IDI-09

“What I really do, especially face-to-face, is see that they have a hard time understanding English. We also have a seating plan, so I prioritize them in the front if possible. Because if they do not understand, at least I can give them other samples. I use my mother tongue more to adjust, but it depends on the student.

Especially when my student is in a board course, I do not use my mother tongue very much.” – IDI-10

“I usually seek feedback from the guidance office since we have student-instructor evaluations. After evaluation, I am able to read if the implementation is okay, if it is appropriate for the student, and if they feel satisfied or somewhat comfortable with the policies I am implementing, especially the way we talk and the way we present them to our students.” – IDI-01

“I have this teacher, a co-worker of mine, with whom I can share my experiences inside the classroom. It is a good thing to have a co-worker who you can confide; you can ask for suggestions from them, and in my case, it is a huge help to me because, aside from being an education major, he is the type of person who is manageable in terms of disciplining the students and also in terms of how, let us say, discuss things. And then, through that, I also have an idea of how to deal with the students.” – IDI-02

“I approached my program head asking for help on how to handle this child.” – IDI-03

“To my peers: I shared that particular experience with my co-teachers. And according to them, I did the right thing. Because once you let them, the child will only develop that kind of behavior, and at least, while early on, you can correct them that what they are doing is wrong.” – IDI-06

“Personally, when there is a problem or anything, the only people we can easily ask for advice from are the faculty where we belong, colleagues, and especially our program head.” – IDI-07

“When it is the end of the semester, I have an activity that is done where it’s like a blank piece of paper and I put my name on it. We all go around, and I tell them to write down anything that you want to tell me if you understand my lesson and everything else or what your comment is regarding mine. I do it with all my students.” – IDI-10

“I will ask my co-instructors if they have experienced this with my students. I will ask them if this has happened or if they have experienced this, and what should be done correctly to address him.” – IDI-11

“I usually find support or clarification from my colleagues. Especially those colleagues who handle the same group of students, and aside from asking my colleagues, most of that we tend also to go to the program head or maybe to the program coordinator.” – IDI-12

“I ask other instructors if they have encountered the same situation as what I have. If that specific student is also misbehaving in their class, or if this particular student has the same approach as my other colleague, if they do the same, I ask them how they reacted and what approach they used when having a conversation with the student, because I think I can also learn to adjust with my student based on the experiences of my colleagues. And aside from that, I could still ask for feedback from their classmate, who is also a student, to validate if that student or that particular student is really kind of misbehaving to clarify the behavior that they have shown me and how the student acts when it comes to the other instructor. So, I also validate that for the students.” – IDI-13

Setting Clear Expectations at the Beginning of a Course or Program

The theme focuses on the importance of setting clear expectations at the beginning of the course or program, as it helps the college instructors set the tone of the classroom. By articulating precise guidelines encompassing communication protocols and behavioral expectations, instructors foster an environment conducive to productive engagement and mutual understanding. Clear expectations not only mitigate potential misunderstandings but also provide students with a structured framework for navigating their academic responsibilities. This strategy enables instructors to effectively manage student interactions, encourage respectful communication, and uphold professionalism throughout the course. Ultimately, setting clear expectations serves as a foundational strategy for promoting a positive and harmonious learning environment.

During the interview, Gentle (pseudonym) pointed out his management of the challenges of academic instruction by emphasizing the imposition of formal behavior and personalities discussed with students before the start of the subject. By setting clear expectations regarding behavior and demeanor from the outset, Gentle (pseudonym) seeks to establish a structured and respectful learning environment. Gentle (pseudonym) mentioned:

“I really imposed formal behavior, personalities nga gina discussed sa ilaha before mag start ang akoang subject. Mura ba’g for the information of the entire sem, mao gyud na akong e apil sa orientation nila.” (IDI-01)

(I really imposed formal behavior and personalities that are discussed with them before my subject starts. It is like the information for the entire semester; that is what I always include in the organization.)

As with the other participant, Kindhearted (pseudonym) highlights his approach to maintaining boundaries and clarity in their interactions with students. He emphasizes the importance of setting clear expectations from the beginning of the class, focusing only on academic concerns. He also acknowledges a degree of empathy and willingness to listen to personal concerns when appropriate. Despite this, Kindhearted (pseudonym) maintains boundaries by directing students to appropriate resources or support systems for non-

academic issues. He stated:

“From the start I made things as clear to them, yun bang klaro sa kanila. I see to it that I only cater concerns relating to academe. In terms of personal na, I, sometimes, I just listen and I try to channel them to the right person na makatutulong sa kanila.” (IDI-02)

(From the start, I made things clear to them. I see to it that I only cater to concerns relating to academia. In terms of personal, sometimes I just listen, and I try to channel them to the right person who can help them.)

Additionally, Cultural Compassionate (pseudonym) focuses on the importance of clear communication, as it is a fundamental strategy for managing challenges in academic instruction. By prioritizing effective communication, Cultural Compassionate (pseudonym) aims to ensure that their expectations, and course requirements are clearly conveyed to students. This approach helps to minimize misunderstandings and conflict, thereby promoting effective communication between her students. She said:

“Clear communication. Ensuring that my instruction and expectation is na communicate nako effectively towards sa akong mga students.” (IDI-07)

(Clear communication. Ensuring that my instruction and expectations are communicated effectively to my students.)

In addition, Firm Facilitator (pseudonym) added emphasizes the importance of setting clear expectations and establishing authority with his students. By defining what is expected of students during class sessions. This approach helps him to ensure that students understand their responsibilities and the consequences of not adhering to the established rules. By implementing this technique, this seeks to maintain control over the classroom dynamics and promote an atmosphere conducive to effective teaching and learning. He pointed:

“My techniques and strategies, is that you really need to establish rules and regulations on set of the semester. You need to establish authority with your students you know. During your class, what are the things that your students, need to do.” - IDI-08

(My technique and strategy are that you really need to establish rules and regulations for each set of semesters. You need to establish authority with your students, you know. During your class, what are the things that your students need to do.)

Moreover, Balance (pseudonym) expressed the importance of establishing a routine or a specific flow of conversation in academic interactions. She describes this strategy of providing a brief orientation to students before addressing their concerns, though in an informal manner. By doing so, Balance (pseudonym) set the stage for effective communication by orienting the student and establishing a structured flow of conversation. She stated:

“Establishing a routine or establishing a particular flow of the conversation. Before we would start, I would always give something somewhat like an orientation to that particular student, but it is not that formal. It is quite like orienting the student before we deal with the concern so that I can establish a flow of communication.” (IDI-12)

Furthermore, Guiding Beacon (pseudonym) emphasize the importance of establishing clear boundaries and standards from the outset of the class. He begins by providing an orientation to the students, asserting their role as the instructor and establishing the dynamic of teacher-student relationships. By setting these boundaries early on, Guiding Beacon (pseudonym) can create a structured and disciplined learning environment. He mentioned:

“At the very beginning of the class, I already gave them the orientation, I am always their instructor, and I already set the boundary that they are my students and I am their teacher. To maintain that kind of standard and boundary, I have a set of rules in my class that they need to follow, and if a particular rule is violated, it means there’s a kind of behavior or misbehavior that particular student is showing.” (IDI-13)

Lastly, Approachable (pseudonym) shared her strategy, which establishes a set of rules or guidelines at the beginning of their class. These rules serve as a framework for behavior and conduct within the classroom. Additionally, the rules act as a form of boundary-setting, allowing us to enforce discipline and maintain order when necessary. She said:

“Naga set sad og rules or house rules naa na siya. Gina set nimo aron e lay nimo sa ilaha ang guards nga kabalo na sila unsa e expect sa imong klase.” (IDI-14)

(I also set rules, or house rules. You set it up so that you can lay the guards on them so that they know what to expect from your class.)

Correcting Improper Behavior Immediately

The theme focuses on the immediate correction of improper behavior by the college instructors when students fail to address it with respect or professionalism. Instead of addressing the matter in front of the class, teachers use this strategy to speak with the student in private. This therefore emphasizes how crucial it is to keep an appropriate and professional learning atmosphere where students are aware of and understand the expected norms for behavior and communication. By addressing improper behavior immediately and privately, teachers aim to correct the behavior and reinforce appropriate conduct without causing embarrassment or confrontation for the student.

As with Gentle (pseudonym), instead of reprimanding the student publicly, he will have a one-on-one conversation to address the issue privately. During this conversation, Gentle (pseudonym) provides guidance and instructions to the student, explaining what they did wrong and how they should behave in the future. By handling the situation in this manner, they can avoid causing embarrassment or offense to the student while still ensuring that they understand the correct behavior. Gentle (pseudonym) shared:

“Ang akong ginabuhay kasagaran jud is I call the attention of the student. Ako silang ginapatawag mismo one-on-one para nga didto nako sila ma briefing, ma storyahan, ma guide og matagaan og kanang mura bag ing-ani imong buhaton the next time nga dili siya offended sa iya nga part kay wala nakabalo iyahang classmate.” (IDI-01)

(What I usually do is call the attention of the student. I call them one-on-one so that I can brief them, talk to them, guide them, and tell them that this is what you should do next time, which he will not get offended by because his classmate did not know.)

In addition, Kindhearted (pseudonym) shared his coping mechanism to address issues or problems with a student directly and personally. Instead of ignoring the problem or addressing it indirectly, he chooses to communicate with the student one-on-one to acknowledge the issue and provide guidance for correction. By having a personal conversation with the student, Kindhearted (pseudonym) can address the problem directly, discuss its impact, and offer suggestions or solutions for improvement. He said:

“One way to cope is to tell the student personally that there is already a problem, to correct her or him in a sense.” (IDI-02)

Moreover, Compassionate Caretaker (pseudonym) describes her approach to addressing a specific behavior issue with a student promptly and privately. She intends to speak directly with the student without delay. In addition, by addressing the issue privately, she can provide feedback and guidance to the student in a more personal and constructive manner. She shared:

“Akoa gyud dayon na siyang ginapatawag, I talk to them privately nga ingnon gyud nako nga dili ko ganahan sa imohang mga reactions, medyo napat-as ta og tingog. So mao to siya, akoa jud na siyang privately gina storyahan.” (IDI-03)

(I really call him right away. I will talk to them privately to tell them that I do not like your reactions. You are raising your voice a bit. And that's it; I talk to them privately.)

Furthermore, Nurturing (pseudonym) highlights how he addressed a situation where a student forgot to greet them or show the expected level of respect. Instead of waiting for the student to initiate the greeting, he takes the initiative to greet the student first, using the student's name (Dong) to draw attention to the lapse in etiquette. By doing so, he employs a form of reverse psychology, subtly reminding the student of the expected behavior and subtly correcting them without directly reprimanding or embarrassing them. He mentioned:

“I always call the attention of the students especially pag naa na gani ta didtoa noh. Kana ganing time nga oy, murag nakalimot naman ka, dong, murag lahi naman ka karon. Good morning, dong, ako na lay mag good morning sa iyaha nga instead siyay mag good morning sa akoa. Murag naa nay reverse psychology directly nga akong gina buhat sa iya or sa ilaha.” (IDI-05)

(I always call the attention of the students. At that time, the student seemed to have forgotten. Dong, you seem to be different now. Good morning, Dong. I will say good morning to him instead of him saying good morning to me. It is like there is a reverse psychology directly that I am doing to him or them.)

Besides, Empowering (pseudonym) expressed that instead of postponing or avoiding difficult conversations, she chooses to confront the students immediately when a problem arises. By doing so, she can address the issue while it is still fresh and relevant, allowing for a more effective resolution. She pointed:

“The techniques that I used is, confronting the students immediately.” (IDI-06)

In addition, Guiding Beacon (pseudonym) expressed that he coped with the situation by actively monitoring and addressing student behavior in the classroom to ensure that students were aware of their actions and behaviors. He takes a proactive approach by consistently calling for the attention of students when they engage in inappropriate actions or misbehavior. By doing so, he can prevent students from being unaware of the consequences of their actions. He stated:

“I do not let that student to not be aware of their actions and that's why I always call their attention. I always correct them every time they do that wrong action or misbehavior. So, those are my techniques.” (IDI-13)

Lastly, Approachable (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of directly addressing students when they exhibit improper behavior. Approachable (pseudonym) suggests that it is necessary to call the attention of the students individually and speak to them personally about their behavior. By doing so, he can ensure that students are aware of their actions and understand why their behavior is inappropriate. He mentioned:

“You have to call the attention of the students nga nag ing-ana sa imoha. Storyahon nimo siya personally. So, mao ng imoha siyang istoryahon para mabal-an gyud nimo nganong ingon ana siya.” (IDI-14)

(You have to call the attention of the students. You will tell them personally. You will talk to them so that they will be able to know.)

Establishing Boundaries and Authority in the Class

The theme focuses on creating a structured and respectful learning environment through clear boundaries and establishing authority by clearly defining expectations, rules, and standards of behavior. Moreover, the theme highlights the critical role of boundaries and authority in facilitating meaningful and productive communication between instructors and students, thereby enhancing the overall teaching and learning experience.

During the interview, Kindhearted (pseudonym) stated the importance of establishing clear roles and boundaries between students and teachers before entering the classroom, highlighting the fundamental dynamics of the classroom. However, he also acknowledges the need for adaptability in his approach to handling students. This flexibility may involve adjusting teaching methods, communication styles, or disciplinary strategies to effectively engage with students and foster a positive learning environment. Kindhearted (pseudonym) stated:

“Before you enter the classroom, dapat klaro sa kanila. I am the student and you are a teacher. Nagkakaroon lang ng adjustment on how you handle them so far. Looking back always to myself to figure out if there are things that I need to change or improve para mas mapaganda or mas maging okay yung tinatawag nating student-teacher relationship” (IDI-02)

(Before you enter the classroom, it should be clear to them. I am the student, and you are a teacher. There is only an adjustment in how you handle them so far. I always look back at myself to figure out if there are things that I need to change or improve to improve the so-called student-teacher relationship.)

As with the other participant, Compassionate Caretaker (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of maintaining clear differences between the roles of teacher and student within the classroom. This also claimed that it was necessary for the teachers to physically stand up, symbolizing their authority and position of leadership over the students. In addition, she acknowledges that while they may be comfortable bonding with students outside of the classroom, such as in social settings, once inside the classroom, they adopt a strict demeanor to establish boundaries and maintain order. She pointed:

“Dapat gyud na nimo mabarogan kay dili jud pwede nga ka level mo sa imong estudyante. Sa gawas, okay kaayo ko ma bonding nila pero pag sa sulod very strict gyud ko. Mao na siya ang para sa ako para naa mi boundaries, both parties.” (IDI-03)

(You really have to stand up because you cannot be on the same level as your student. Outside, I am okay with bonding with them, but inside, I am very strict. For me, there should be boundaries between both parties.)

In addition, Attentive Observer (pseudonym) emphasizes that she prioritized discussing only the specific concerns raised by students. If a student brings up topics unrelated to the concern at hand, she redirects the conversation back to the relevant issue and refrains from entertaining off-topic discussions. Thus, by maintaining focus and boundaries, she can ensure that communication remains productive, purposeful, and respectful of the established professional relationship between teacher and student. She said:

“As much as possible when talking to the students, kung unsa lang gani to ang ilahang concerns mao lang gyud to akoang e address, mao lang gyud to akoang storyahan. Kung naa man galing instances wherein nalayo na sa topic or naa nay gusto e discuss ang student wherein dili naman siya part sa concern. I have to make it away pud as well na dili pud dayon nako e entertain. Though, e-acknowledge nako nga naa siya other concern about ato, pero I have to remind the student nga dili nato siya part sa concern or kung unsa man gani to. Kay naa man gud uban na sa sobra nato ka comfortable always nato gina entertain ang thoughts maskin na dili na siya labot gud sa unsa man to nga concern mao na karon nga maging mag deviate na ta didto sa atoang purpose and at the same time medyo mawala na ta sa atoang boundaries.” (IDI-04)

(As much as possible, when talking to the students, if they have any concerns, that is the only thing I can talk about. If there are instances where the student has gone beyond the topic or wants to discuss something that is not part of the concern, I do not entertain it right away. Although I will acknowledge the concern, I have to remind the student that it is not part of the concern, or whatever the reason is. Because some other students are too comfortable with us, we always entertain their thoughts even though they are no longer involved in any concern, so now we are deviating from our purpose, and at the same time we are losing our boundaries.)

Moreover, Nurturing (pseudonym) shared his approach to maintaining clear boundaries between their roles as teachers and their personal relationships with students. He emphasizes that within the classroom or school setting, they maintain a professional role and expect students to recognize and respect their authority as educators. However, outside of the school environment, Nurturing (pseudonym) adopts a more casual and friendly relationship with students. By identifying these boundaries, teachers can ensure that they can fulfill their responsibilities as teachers effectively while also fostering positive and respectful relationships with students. He shared:

“I really separate. Naa jud koy separation sa teacher and student. Ako gyud ng gina maintain na kung estudyante ta diri sa sulod, estudyante tika diri sa sulod, barkada tika sa gawas. So, you have to respect me pag naa ta sa diri sa eskwelahan. Kay kung naa ta sa gawas, barkada ta. Kay there are some student man gud pag barkada ta sa gawas, madala na niya diri. Pag naa gani ta diri, teacher ko nimo. Pag naa ta sa gawas, barkada taka. So, isa na sya. I have my boundaries I have to maintain nga ang kana ganing ang akoang role as diri sa opisina og sa ah kung unsa pud ko nga teacher.” (DI-05)

(I really separate. I have a separation between teacher and student. I am the one who maintains that you are my students inside and I am your friend outside. So, you have to respect me when we are here at school. Because when we are out, we are friends. Because there are some students who are friends outside, they will bring it inside the school. When we are here, I am your teacher. When we are out, we are friends. I have my boundaries; I have to maintain that this is my role here in the office and in what kind of teacher I am.)

Besides, Firm Facilitator (pseudonym) explained the crucial role of the teacher in establishing authority within the classroom environment. He suggests that the level of formality and respect exhibited by students is directly influenced by the teacher's demeanor and level of authority. If the teacher demonstrates a lack of concern or authority, students may perceive a lower level of formality and may not take the learning environment as seriously. He said:

"It is up on the teacher on how a teacher establish authority inside the class because if you're students can see nga walay pakialam si teacher nga walay pakialam sa imong gina buhat, so that is the time that the level of formality inside the classroom will be low. But if you are really highly authoritative inside the classroom, so, that is the time the level of formality as well as high. Meaning, your students are cooperating with you, you students are listening with you as well." (IDI-08)

(It is up to the teacher to establish authority inside the class because if your students observe that the teacher does not care about what you are doing, then the level of formality inside the classroom will be low. But if you are really highly authoritative inside the classroom, then the level of formality will be high. Meaning, your students are cooperating with you, and they are listening to you as well.)

Furthermore, Welcoming (pseudonym) suggests against engaging in discussions or addressing questions that stray beyond the purpose of the academic context. Specifically, if a student asks a question that is not directly related to the subject matter being taught, teachers should refrain from providing an answer. This approach helps to uphold the professionalism of the instructor-student relationship and ensures that the focus remains on academic matters. She emphasized:

"Para ma maintain jud nato ang professional boundary is don't go beyond topics nga outside na siya sa unsay purpose nimo. If you are instructors of course you have to deal with questions nga about sa academics. What if imohang estudyante mag ask of course, ayaw pag answer og question nga kabalo ka nga beyond na sa imohang una nga gina tudlo nga subject. Kato, focus lang ta didtosa unsa imong purpose and what's the purpose of that nga nag communicate imong estudyante." (IDI-09)

(To maintain the professional boundary, do not go beyond topics that are outside of your purpose. If you are an instructor, of course you have to deal with questions about academics. What if your student asks? Of course, do not answer a question that you know is beyond the scope of what you are teaching. That's it. Let us just focus on what your purpose is and what's the purpose of that when your student communicates.)

Meanwhile, Adaptive (pseudonym) explained that she typically does not share personal information with their students, thereby preserving a level of distance and professionalism. By keeping their personal life separate from their role as an instructor, Adaptive (pseudonym) ensures that students focus on the subject matter and their academic development rather than on personal details about the teacher. She said:

"Usually, when I talk to my students or having our class, dili man pud gud kaayo ko ga disclose sa akong mga students so murag na maintain gihapon nako ang boundary. Dili kaayo sila kabalo sa akong personal space. More likely pud, during my classes, akong gina example usually kadtong maencounter man pud sa akong mga students dili man pud about sa ako. So, murag at least dili kaayo sya maka unsa." (IDI-10)

(Usually, when I talk to my students or have our class, I do not really disclose much to my students, so it seems like I still maintain the boundary. They do not know much about my personal space. More likely, during my classes, I usually set an example for those who meet my students, not about me.)

Consequently, Empathetic (pseudonym) emphasize the importance of maintaining a clear distinction between the roles of students and teachers within the classroom environment. She advises students to remember their role as learners and to address their teacher with appropriate formality and respect. She asserts that while students and teachers may have a more informal relationship outside of the classroom, inside the educational setting, the teacher-student dynamic should be upheld. She pointed:

"Keep reminding them na students mo og kung teacher mag address og formality. Pero og sa gawas kaila ta pero og diri sa classroom teacher ko nimo, dili mo magpa labi og kanang pagara." (IDI-11)

(Keep reminding them that you are students, and if a teacher, address formality. But if we are outside, we know each other. But here in the classroom, I am your teacher, and do not act improperly.)

Lastly, Approachable (pseudonym) intends to emphasize the importance of setting clear boundaries with students in order to maintain professionalism and manage the teacher-student relationship effectively. Additionally, she mentioned the need for clear communication regarding expectations for student behavior, responses, and the nature of concerns or questions that are appropriate within the academic setting. She shared:

“Mag himo og clear na like set nga clear boundaries sa students nga kani lang ang dapat nako itubag or dapat ang concerns is related sa academic or topic dili mga personal or inappropriate questions. Ing-ana lang para ma maintain jud og ma manage ang professional boundaries.” (IDI-14)

(Make it clear, like setting clear boundaries with the students, that this is how you should respond or that the concerns should be related to the academic topic, not personal or inappropriate questions. That is just to maintain and manage professional boundaries.)

Building Good Rapport through a Supportive Teacher-Student Relationship

The theme revolves around the idea of fostering positive connections between instructors and students. It emphasizes the importance of nurturing supportive, respectful, and trusting relationships to enhance the overall learning experience. This theme underscores the significant role that a strong teacher-student relationship plays in promoting student engagement, motivation, and academic success. Additionally, it highlights the benefits of mutual respect, effective communication, and empathetic understanding in creating a conducive learning environment where students feel valued, supported, and empowered to reach their full potential. Furthermore, this theme emphasizes the importance of building and maintaining positive rapport between instructors and students as a cornerstone of effective teaching and learning in college.

During the interview, Compassionate Caretaker (pseudonym) expressed that outside of the classroom, teachers are open to forming friendships with their students, allowing for a more informal and friendly dynamic. However, once they are inside the classroom, they maintain their role as the instructor, and students are expected to show respect accordingly. Thus, by establishing this boundary, it can create a clear distinction between personal relationships and professional expectations within the educational setting, and students will respect her as their instructor. Compassionate Caretaker (pseudonym) mentioned:

“Para ma kuan nako ni nga mga challenges, akoa sila gina friend. Sa gawas, akoa jud sila gina friend and at least pag naa na mi sa sulod ang akoang pagka instructor ilaha jud na erespeto.” (IDI-03)

(For me to overcome these challenges, I make friends with them. Outside, they can call me their friend, and at least if we are inside, I am their instructor, they need to respect me.)

As with the other participants, Nurturing (pseudonym) coped with the challenges by remaining empathetic and understanding, recognizing that a student's behavior or performance in class may be influenced by external factors or personal issues. To effectively address these challenges, Nurturing (pseudonym) mentions that she takes a deliberate and patient approach. Instead of reacting impulsively, even when feeling frustrated or angry, she prioritized communication and understanding. She pointed:

“Strategies kay different characteristics, different asa sila gikan. Especially, kanang mga bata karon nga gikan sa mga lagyo, gikan sa problema nga naa sa balay, so, I need also to adjust and even sa ako personally, sa ako mga estudyante, gina butang nako always sa akong utok nga hala oy, basin naa ni problema ning bata ani. So, I evaluate and ask to the other person unsay problema ato niya, ngano man. And mahibal-an, nako, ah okay. So, I need to hinay-hinay noh baskin suko na kaayo ka kailangan.” (IDI-05)

(Since they have different characteristics and different places where they come from. Especially those children today who come from far away, they have problem at home, so I also need to adjust, and even for me personally, for my students, I always keep in mind that maybe this child has a problem. So, I evaluate and ask the other person what the problem is and why. And for me to know. So, I need to take it slowly, even though I am already angry.)

In addition, Cultural Compassionate (pseudonym) stated that by fostering a classroom environment where students feel comfortable sharing their thoughts and ideas, the teacher can promote more open and effective communication. This not only allows students to express themselves but also helps to clarify any misunderstandings and encourages active engagement in the learning process. Furthermore, she emphasized that learning should not be solely dependent on the teacher. Both students and teachers play active roles in the educational process, with valuable insights and contributions coming from both sides. She shared:

“In effective formal communication between the teacher and student eventually leads to frustration and also misunderstanding on both sides. And what are my actions or techniques to improve this is... kana lang, encourage participation among students and aside from that is number one jud is paminawon ang ilahang constraints and then dili lang man ang teachers-students kay purely from the teacher noh ang information and learning is coming from both man, students and teacher.” (IDI-07)

(Effective formal communication between the teacher and student eventually leads to frustration and misunderstanding on both sides. And what are my actions or techniques to improve this is to encourage participation among students, and aside from that, number one is to listen to their constraints, and then not only the teacher-students, because the information and learning are coming purely from the teacher, both students and teachers.)

Lastly, Approachable (pseudonym) pointed out the importance of establishing a supportive and comfortable environment for students within the classroom. This emphasizes the role of the teacher in creating a sense of friendship and camaraderie with students, particularly for those who may not feel open or comfortable with their family or friends outside of school. By fostering a positive relationship with students, the teacher provides them with a "comfort zone" where they can feel accepted, understood, and valued. She stated:

“Makig close pud ka aron maka feel siya nga naa siyay room for... naa siyay comfort zone nga ma feel sa imoha nga ay pwede ra diay kay naa man gud uban noh nga dili open sa atong family, sa atoang friends. Naa gyud certain person nga murag gaan atong buot, nga mas maka communicate ta, so ing-ana sya.” (IDI-14)

(You will make friends with them so that they can feel that they have a comfort zone and that it is okay because there are some who are not open to their family and to their friends. There is a certain person with whom we feel our hearts light and with whom we can communicate better.)

Having an Understanding on the Various Underlying Reasons of Students' Misbehaviors

The theme highlights the importance of empathy and understanding for college instructors in fostering effective communication with their students. Through analyzing the root causes of misbehaviors, teachers can gain a deeper understanding of the motivations behind them; it could be the student's personal problems, difficulties in the classroom, or outside stressors. With this perspective, teachers can address disciplinary issues with compassion and modify their communication tactics to target the root causes rather than only responding to outward actions. Furthermore, college instructors can create a supportive learning atmosphere where students feel trust and rapport with each other by recognizing and resolving these underlying causes.

From the interview, Compassionate Caretaker (pseudonym) believes in building personal connections with her students as a strategy to overcome challenges in the classroom. By befriending her students, Compassionate Caretaker (pseudonym) aims to establish a rapport that fosters mutual respect and cooperation. Moreover, she also emphasizes having a balance that promotes a positive learning environment while maintaining authority and respect in an educational setting. Compassionate Caretaker (pseudonym) stated:

“Ang akoa gyung coping mechanism ani is naa pud mga pagsabot, akoa silang gina-ingna kung unsa ang batasan nila sa ilang panimalay dili nila dal-on sa skwelahan.” (IDI-03)

(For me to overcome these challenges, I make friends with them. Outside, they can call me their friend, and at least if we are inside, I am their instructor, so they need to respect me.)

As with the other participant, Attentive Observer (pseudonym) emphasizes the necessity of patience in handling student's mistakes and misbehavior in the classroom. She emphasized that reacting impulsively with anger or scolding when mistakes are made is ineffective. Instead, understand the context behind the student's behavior. By considering factors such as the student's background and prior experiences, the instructor can gain insight into why the student may be struggling or behaving in a certain way. She mentioned:

“Patience jud siguro kay syempre, dili man ta pwede or kami as an instructor nga dili man mi pwede nga ah naa mi nakita nga mali tapos kasab-an dayon namo right away. So, we have to understand first, ngano, asa gikan ang bata, ngano ingon ani mani siya. Maybe because that student wala siya na anad when it comes to formal communication.” (IDI-04)

(There must be patience because, of course, we cannot, or we, as the instructor, cannot act if we spot mistakes and get angry and scold right away. So, we have to understand first: why, where did the child come from, and why he is like this? Maybe because that student is not used to it when it comes to formal communication.)

Moreover, Nurturing (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of empathy and emotional awareness, especially when dealing with students who come from diverse backgrounds and may have various challenges. Additionally, by "deepening and widening" his emotions, even in moments of anger or frustration, Nurturing (pseudonym) manages to make a deliberate effort to empathize with their students' perspectives and circumstances. He said:

“Naghinay-hinay og adjust due to ah I need to adjust also kay kailangan man nako tan-awon sa bata. Naa man gud lahi-lahi nga gi agian, problems ang bata. So, I need to deepen and to widen my emotion, may kanang kuan hmmm baskin suko na kaayo ka. Ano lang, mag careful lang gyud ka in dealing with people nga a lot of daghan kaayo nga environment nga nagka lahi-lahi.” (IDI-05)

(I am slowly adjusting because I need to look at the child. There are students who have different experiences and problems. So, I need to deepen and widen my emotions, even when you are angry. Just be careful when dealing with people, especially those who have different environments.)

In addition, Empathetic (pseudonym) expressed in response to situations where students perceive it as being angry; even though she is not, she adopts a patient and understanding approach by asking the student directly about their emotions rather than immediately reacting to the perceived anger. By seeking clarification and communication, Empathetic (pseudonym) demonstrates a willingness to address misunderstandings and resolve conflicts constructively through understanding the root of the misbehavior. She said:

“Parehas sa akoa, abi nilag nasuko ko pero wala diay so, ako pud kung ing-ana akong panan-aw mangutana ko kung nasuko ka. Mangutana ko, dili dayon ko mureact sa iyang reaction sa iyang tubag sa akoa. Mangutana ko og nasuko ka gang? Wala man ma' am nag explain lang. mao ra to siya.” (IDI-11)

(It is the same thing with me; they think I am angry, but I am not. So, I will also ask. I will not immediately react to the reaction or his response to me. I asked if he was angry, and they also explained that he was not.)

Meanwhile, Balance (pseudonym) highlights her willingness to approach situations with empathy and understanding rather than resorting to aggression, particularly when students exceed established boundaries. Balance (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of considering the context and emotions and taking into account the individual circumstances and feelings of the student. She shared:

“I would say that I will always have the principle of consideration. In some cases, if I find the concern or if I find the student going beyond the boundary that I have said, I will not always approach him or her in an aggressive manner but rather consider the possible scenario or possible feeling or emotion of that particular student at that time, so I will be able to adjust my response or reaction to his or her actions or to the words that have been used.” (IDI-12)

Furthermore, Guiding Beacon (pseudonym) believed that instead of immediately assuming that a student is misbehaving, try to ask questions to gain a deeper understanding of the situation. By inquiring about the reasons behind the student's actions, he can confirm whether the behavior constitutes misbehavior or if there are underlying factors at play. He stated:

“I try to ask them questions: Why are you misbehaving and why are you showing those actions? I ask questions so that I can really confirm if that student is misbehaving or not.” (IDI-13)

Lastly, Approachable (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of sensitivity and awareness of individual differences among students, particularly regarding their backgrounds and upbringings. She highlights the diversity in communication styles, noting that some students may appear to be shouting even when they are simply speaking. This observation emphasizes the need for instructors to recognize and adapt to varying communication preferences and cultural norms. By acknowledging these differences, instructors can develop tailored strategies for effectively engaging with students from diverse backgrounds. She pointed:

“Kani need pud ka nga maging sensitive sa ilaha kay lahi-lahi man sila og background, lahi-lahi silag upbringing ing-ana. Naay uban tao nga hong-hong ra diay sa iya pero singgit na sa imoha. So, mga ingon ana ba, nag storya raman ko pero murag singgit na. so, lahi-lahi gyud ang imohang pag handle og strategies sa ilaha kay kung ikaw man gud dili man gud nimo iparehas sa tanan ang imohang pagdala sa ilaha sa mga bata kay lahi-lahi man gyud na sila.” (IDI-14)

(You also need to be sensitive to them because they have different backgrounds and different upbringings. There are other people who are just talking to you but look like they are shouting at you, situations like that. You really have different strategies for handling them because they are different.)

Implementing a Policy of Language Used Inside the Classroom

The theme focuses on establishing guidelines or rules regarding language usage within the educational setting to facilitate effective communication. This policy implemented by the college instructors aims to promote clarity, respect, and inclusivity among students and instructors. By defining acceptable language and communication norms, the policy helps maintain a conducive learning environment where all individuals feel valued and understood. Additionally, such a policy may address issues such as inappropriate language, offensive speech, or discriminatory remarks, fostering a culture of mutual respect and professionalism. Moreover, implementing a language policy can support language development and academic success by emphasizing the use of clear and respectful communication strategies inside the classroom.

During the interview, Gentle (pseudonym) outlines a specific language implementation policy for the classroom environment. He emphasized the importance of using English consistently for all activities, instructions, discussions, and deliberations while inside the classroom. This rule aims to create a language-immersive environment conducive to English language learning and communication skills development. Gentle (pseudonym) shared:

“Classroom implementation policies. Bali sa classroom, naa lang mi gina follow nga mao na language na amo gamiton. Stick to English language na amo gamiton basta naa mi sa classroom and even bisag unsa nga activities, instructions, tanan, deliberations, discussions basta naa sa classroom we speak English. Aside from that dili nako gina allow-- gina discourage. But sometimes ga allow kog ing-ana nga cases kung need e apply. For example, tagalog gyud kay dili gyud makaya sir, sige I will allow to taglish noh other than that na mga languages or unsa ba nga ilang ginagamit nga kabalo sila, ako lang gina allow only the time nga naa mi activity nga need to siya sa presentation kay kung dili man gud siya applicable, wala nako gina allow. Mura ba'g specified sa akong communication rules policies nga other ani nga atoang language nga gamiton, you can use that if the application sa atoang sitwasyon maapply siya.” (IDI-01)

(Classroom implementation policies. In the classroom, we only follow the language that we use. Stick to the English language that we will use as long as we are in the classroom, and even for any activities, instructions, everything, deliberations, and discussions, as long as we are in the classroom, we speak English. Aside from that, I do not allow it; I discourage it. But sometimes I allow such cases if they need to apply. For example, Tagalog, because they are having a hard time. I will allow it to use Taglish other than those languages, or whatever they use that they know. I only allow them to use Taglish when we have an activity that needs to be included in the presentation; if it is not applicable, I do not allow it. It should be specified in my communication rules and policies that our language will be used differently. You can only use it if it is applicable to our situation.)

As with the other participant, Firm Facilitator (pseudonym) emphasizes that proficiency in the English language is a prerequisite for

these students, as they are preparing to become practitioners in the field. Therefore, it is essential for them to consistently practice and use English during discussions and activities. However, he also supports students' comprehension and participation while still prioritizing the use of English as the primary language of instruction and communication. By permitting controlled code-switching, Firm Facilitator (pseudonym) strikes a balance between encouraging English proficiency and accommodating students' linguistic needs and abilities. He stated:

"I am teaching English major students and that is why it's really a prerequisite for them to use the English language kay they don't have any other choice because they are the future practitioners of the English language. Maybe, this is the perfect time for them to practice their English language during our discussion they need to practice using the English language. but there are sometimes if I can really see if the students are struggling but I can sense nga naa siyay idea, so now that is the time allowing my students to code switch but not totally speak in Bisaya. Only code mixing and code switching." (IDI-08)

(I am teaching English major students, and that is why it is really a prerequisite for them to use the English language. They do not have any other choice because they are the future practitioners of the English language. Maybe this is the perfect time for them to practice their English language during our discussion. But there are times when I can really see if the students are struggling, but I can sense that he has an idea, so now is the time to allow my students to code switch but not totally speak Bisaya. Only code mixing and code switching.)

In addition, Welcoming (pseudonym) highlights the dual role of English and Bisaya as mediums of instruction in a diverse classroom setting. She explains that English is typically used as the primary language of instruction, as it is commonly understood by students from various linguistic backgrounds. However, Welcoming (pseudonym) also recognizes that some students may struggle with English or find it difficult to comprehend certain announcements or information. In such cases, the instructor employs Bisaya, to ensure effective communication and accommodate the linguistic diversity of the students. She said:

"Usual man jud nato gina gamit kay baskin pag diverse ang student murag tanan man siguro maka sabot og English ba dira or Bisaya. So, mga medium of instruction na imong gamiton. Kung dili gyud or maglisod sila para more emphasis sa imong announcement or unsa imong gusto e inform sa imong mga estudyante kana, mugamit ka og Bisaya para ma deal nimo ang diversity sa student." (IDI-09)

(We usually use English because, even if the student is diverse, it seems like everyone can understand English or Bisaya. and we use it as our medium of instruction. If they cannot or they find it difficult, we can put more emphasis on the announcement or what you want to inform your students. You use Bisaya so that you can deal with the diversity of the students.)

Lastly, Adaptive (pseudonym) shared her approach to addressing language barriers in the classroom, particularly for students who may struggle with understanding English. She observes student's difficulties during face-to-face interactions and utilizes strategies to support their comprehension. One such strategy involves implementing a seating plan where students who face challenges with English are prioritized in the front rows. This positioning allows the instructor to provide additional examples or explanations directly to these students, enhancing their understanding. She pointed:

"Ang akong ginabuhat man gud is if labi na gyud face-to-face makita nako maglisod silag sabot sa English naa man tay katong seat plan so mas gina prioritize nako to sila sa front kung possible. Kay kung wala sila nakasabot, at least mahatagan nako silag other samples. And kung mas duol sila sa akoo, pag mag bisaya nako mas makasabot sila and symepre mas naga gamit ko og mother tongue na pud to adjust but depende sa student. Especially pag board course akong student, dili kaayo ko ga gamit og mother tongue." (IDI-10)

(What I really do, especially face-to-face, is I see that they have a hard time understanding English. We also have a seating plan, so I prioritize them in the front if possible. Because if they do not understand, at least I can give them other samples. I use my mother tongue more to adjust, but it depends on the student. Especially when my student is in a board course, I don't use my mother tongue very much.)

Strengthening Student-Teacher Communication through Comprehensive Feedback

The theme addresses the multifaceted approach that college instructors take to improve communication with their students. The college instructors actively seek feedback to refine their teaching strategies and communication methods. This includes seeking feedback from colleagues, program heads, and student evaluations to assess the effectiveness of their teaching techniques and classroom management approaches. Moreover, instructors also solicit advice on how to handle challenging student behaviors in the classroom, demonstrating a commitment to fostering a positive and conducive learning environment. By actively seeking and integrating feedback, instructors can enhance their communication skills, optimize their teaching methods, and ultimately improve the overall learning experience for their students.

From the interview, Gentle (pseudonym) shared his strategy which revolves around seeking feedback from the guidance office, particularly through student-instructor evaluations. By utilizing this feedback mechanism, Gentle (pseudonym) gains valuable insights into the effectiveness of his teaching methods and communication approach. He evaluates whether his implementations align with student needs, preferences, and comfort levels, particularly regarding policies related to communication and presentation style. Through

these evaluations, he can assess whether his methods are appropriate and conducive to a positive learning environment. Gentle (pseudonym) shared:

“I seek feedback usually and normally gyud is gikan sa guidance office noh since naa man tay evaluation student-instructor. Diha ra nako mabasa ang feedback kung kato ang akong gi implement okay ba sya, kanang ni angay ba ang studyante noh, are they feel satisfied or somewhat like either unsa na kanang comfortable sa akong gina pa implement nga policies labi na gyud sa correspondence sa kanang sa amoang the way we talk, the way we present sa amoang studyante.” (IDI-01)

(I usually seek feedback from the guidance office since we have student-instructor evaluations. After evaluation, I am able to read if the implementation is okay, if it is appropriate for the student, and if they feel satisfied or somewhat comfortable with the policies I am implementing, especially the way we talk and the way we present them to our students.)

As with the other participant, Kindhearted (pseudonym) shared the importance and benefits of having a supportive colleague with whom the he can share experiences and seek advice regarding classroom management and teaching strategies. By confiding in this colleague, Kindhearted (pseudonym) gains insights into different approaches to handling classroom situations and can receive constructive suggestions for improvement. He stated:

“I have this teacher, co-worker of me who I can share my experiences inside the classroom. Kaya good thing na magkaroon ka ng isang co-worker who you can confine, you can ask suggestions from them and in my case, napakalaking tulong sa akin kasi aside sa education major, he is a type of person who is manageable in terms of disciplining the students, and also sa mga bagay on how let say discuss things. And then, through that, nagkakaroon din ako ng idea on how to deal with the students.” (IDI-02)

(I have this teacher, a co-worker of mine, with whom I can share my experiences inside the classroom. It is a good thing to have a co-worker who you can confine; you can ask for suggestions from them, and in my case, it is a huge help to me because, aside from being an education major, he is the type of person who is manageable in terms of disciplining the students and also in terms of how, let say, discuss things. And then, through that, I also have an idea of how to deal with the students.)

Additionally, Compassionate Caretaker (pseudonym) utilized a coping mechanism for effective communication and professional improvement by seeking guidance from their program head. By recognizing the challenges, she faces with a particular student or situation in the classroom, the individual demonstrates a proactive approach to address the issue and enhance their teaching skills. She said:

“Ni duol jud ko sa akong program head nangayo og tabang unsaon nako pag handle ani nga bata.” (IDI-03)

(I really approached my program head, asking for help on how to handle this child.)

Moreover, Empowering (a pseudonym) emphasized how she shared a specific experience with her fellow teachers, seeking validation and feedback on their approach to handling a challenging situation in the classroom. Which helped her and guided her in facing and replying to the challenges she faced. She pointed:

“Sa akong mga peers. I share that particular experience sa akong co-teachers. And according to them, tama ra pud ang akong gibuhat. Kasi once pabayaon nimo na siya, mudasa ang bata and at least, samtang sayo pa ma correct na nimo sila nga mali diay ang ilang gi buhat.” (IDI-06)

(To my peers. I shared that particular experience with my co-teachers. And according to them, I did the right thing. Because once you let them, the child will only develop that kind of behavior, and at least, while early on, you can correct them that what they are doing is wrong.)

Consequently, Cultural Compassionate (pseudonym) shared that she primarily relies on three main sources for advice: faculty members within their department, colleagues, and the program head. She highlights the importance of seeking support and input from those who are familiar with their professional context and responsibilities. She stated:

“Personally, pag naay problem or anything ang dali gyud namo nga mapangayoan og advice is sa faculty nga asa mi na belong, colleagues, and especially our program head.” (IDI-07)

(Personally, when there is a problem or anything, the only people we can easily ask for advice from are the faculty where we belong, colleagues, and especially our program head.)

Furthermore, Adaptive (pseudonym) describes a specific activity she employs at the end of the semester as a coping mechanism for gathering feedback and insights from her students. The activity involves distributing blank pieces of paper to each student and asking them to write down any thoughts or comments they have regarding her lessons and teaching style. This approach provides an opportunity for students to express their opinions openly and anonymously, without fear of judgment or repercussion. By encouraging feedback through this activity, Adaptive (pseudonym) demonstrates a willingness to listen to her students' perspectives and adapt her teaching methods accordingly. She shared:

“Pag at the end na sa semester, naa koy activity nga gina buhat where in nga mura gud og paper nga blank and ibutang nako ako ang

name didtoa, e rounds na namo sya tanan and ako silang gina ignan nga you right down anything that you wanted to tell me kung nakasabot ba mo sa akong lesson, and everything or unsa ba inyong comment regarding sa akoo. Ginabuhat gyud nako na sa tanan nakong student.” (IDI-10)

(When it is the end of the semester, I have an activity that is done where it is like a blank piece of paper and I put my name on it. We all go around, and I tell them to write down anything that you want to tell me if you understand my lesson and everything else or what your comment is regarding mine. I do it with all my students.)

Meanwhile, Empathetic (pseudonym) shared that she consults with her co-instructors to gather their perspectives and insights on any particular situation or behavior exhibited by a student. She recognizes that her colleagues may have encountered similar situations with her students and could offer valuable advice on how to effectively address the issue. She mentioned:

“Mangutana ko sa co-instructors og naka experience na mo ani sa akong estudyante? Unsa inyong gina buhat? mag ask ko sa ilaha og nahitabo na ba ni or naka experience na ba sila ani og unsay dapat og tama nga buhaton para ma address ni sya.” (IDI-11)

(I will ask my co-instructors if they have experienced this with my students. I will ask them if this has happened or if they have experienced this, and what should be done correctly to address him.)

Added by Balance (pseudonym) she believed in the importance of seeking support and clarification from her colleagues and higher-ups in her academic institution. She values collaboration and recognizes that her colleagues, especially those who handle the same group of students, can offer valuable insights and advice tailored to her specific teaching context. She pointed:

“I usually find support or clarification with my colleagues. Especially, those colleagues who handle the same group of students and aside from asking my colleagues, most of that we tend also to go to the program head or maybe to program coordinator.” (IDI-12)

(I usually find support or clarification from my colleagues. Especially those colleagues who handle the same group of students, and aside from asking my colleagues, most of that we tend also to go to the program head or maybe to the program coordinator.)

Lastly, Guiding Beacon (pseudonym) expressed that he coped with the situations by addressing challenges with student behavior by seeking input and guidance from colleagues and students themselves. He acknowledges that he may not be the only instructor facing a particular student's misbehavior, so Guiding Beacon (pseudonym) reached out to other instructors to inquire about their experiences. By learning how other instructors have dealt with similar situations, he can gain insights into different approaches and strategies for managing student behavior effectively. He stated:

“I ask other instructors if they have encountered the same situation as what I have. If that specific student is also misbehaving in their class, or if this particular student has the same approach as my other colleague, If they do the same, I ask them how they reacted and what approach they used when having a conversation with the student, because I think I can also learn to adjust with my student based on the experiences of my colleagues. And aside from that, I could still ask for feedback from their classmate, who is also a student, to validate if that student or that particular student is really kind of misbehaving to clarify the behavior that they’ve shown me and how the student acts when it comes to the other instructor. So, I also validate that for the students.” (IDI-13)

Research Question No. 3: What are the insights of teachers about formal correspondence with students that they can share with others?

To answer this research question, in-depth interviews were conducted with the participants, respectively. Hence, several sub-questions were asked to share their insights about the formal correspondence with students that they can share with others.

The major themes and core ideas for research question number 3 were presented in table 4. From the answers of the participants, five major themes emerged: to lead is to set by example, the importance of open communication and sense of empathy, the value of cultivating good connection through understanding, consideration, and openness, upholding professionalism and respect with each other, and build a healthy relationship in the learning environment.

Table 4. Insights of the College Instructors in Their Student-Teacher Formal Correspondence

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
To Lead is to Set by Example	<p>“One of the things I want to emphasize, show, or say is respect. Once the student is respected and, at the same time, vice versa, the instructor is respected by the student, effective communication with the student can be maintained once it is well implemented.” – IDI-01</p> <p>“On the instructor's part, what I can see is how they communicate with the students, because based on my observation, there are also instructors who seem to be casual when it comes to the communication they have with the students. It's like they did not set any boundaries there. I'm a teacher, and you are my student. The instructors should also be reminded that you also have boundaries when it comes to the communication that you have with your students. The danger is that the students are too comfortable with you. So, now, instead of that, they will address you in a proper way.” – IDI-04</p> <p>“Whether you are a teacher or a student, the formalities should still be there. Do not leave out the formality when it comes to communication, whether via media or face-to-face. Most especially, you are a professional; wherever you go, you are a professional. So, no matter who you are talking to, you</p>

The Importance of Open Communication and Sense of Empathy

should show professionalism.” – IDI-06

“It starts with you and who you are as an instructor. Let us say, for example, that he is your student, he chats with you, and then you reply, good evening. So, he will reply, good evening, ma'am. For me, how can students respect you if you yourself do not know how to respect them?” – IDI-09

“I maintain formality in making communications with my students or even engaging with them by making myself an example of myself in formality or dealing with people. So, I started showing respect to my students, and they must follow as well. With that, I guess they will see it, and I also wanted to make them do the actions of being polite and respectful.” – IDI-13

“You should deal with your students in a nice way so that they will respect you. It really starts with you: What do you expect from the students that they will show you when you yourself do not deserve to be respected? It really begins with you and how you will present yourself to them.” – IDI-14

“I am very open. When I am in class, I explain and emphasize to them that in the classroom, I do not judge them or put them down, like make them inferior to me. I maintain that one by maybe making myself level with them. It's like if I try to lower myself to their level so that they will not be shy, intimidated, or something, so that our communication can maintain good communication. Because if I implement that and terrorize you, there is a big tendency that our connection and regard for the correspondence itself will be different.” – IDI-01

“I really have to understand my students. There are times when the other instructors see that, like, my student is like this; they judge right away, or they do not understand right away. So, what I have learned from the experiences is that I really have to understand my student's because maybe that is how he is or going through something in life.” – IDI-04

“You have to build rapport and connections with your students. For me, one of the ways to maintain the engagement of the students is if they are afraid to perform in your class, they are not afraid to ask questions, or they are open-minded, and not just open-minded, but always cater to their concerns in your class. Because once the students feel how you deal with them, everything will follow, and they will be engaged. Because if your students are afraid of you, then the more they will be afraid to engage, the more they will be afraid to make mistakes. So, that is probably what we should address. We should really have a connection with your students.” – IDI-09

“I always make sure that their feelings and concerns will not be invalidated, and I will let them feel that they can always come to me or talk to me. Let me say establishing an image of being approachable, but I don't know if that's how they perceive it, but I'm trying to do that by communicating it to them. They can be open with me, they can be honest with me, and they would be free from any possible judgment or biases that they would be hearing unless the particular issue or concern has been treated or has been approached properly.” – IDI- 12

The Value of Cultivating Good Connections through Understanding, Consideration, and Openness

“For me, effective, formal communication is important in the student-instructor connection. Why? Because when it is maintained, the rest will follow. As long as your communication is good, your connection is good, student and teacher; actually, whatever concerns your students say, they will come out. Until it comes to the point that students will be quiet, the communication is not good, students already have a problem, and the instructor did not know that this was his problem because there was no open communication. That's the only way to be open with your students. For me, instructors have the biggest responsibility in terms of that.” – IDI-01

“My insights that I can give are that the teacher should be patient. You must have love for your students, because if you do not love them, it is very easy to let them fail. Because there are times when I'm in class, students are already yawning, and some are sleeping. As their instructor, I learned to really love them. I ask them what their problem is, and because of that, I got their attention—that ma'am is listening to me. It turns out they have a problem. One time, there was a child that I asked because he kept sleeping in my class, but his problem was because they were poor; he was a working student. In that case, the instructor should be considerate too.” – IDI-03

“I will say it again, understanding. Students are not the same as those who came from high-end schools in order to understand right away. There are some students in areas where formal communication is not emphasized. That is why we need to understand and be patient as instructors in order to teach them the proper ways of communicating.” – IDI-04

“At the end of the day, we are still humans, and the student is also human. After you scold him, if you get him down, you need to talk. The only lesson you can learn is to understand each other. If he is your student, after you scolded him for being late, why is he late? There is the end point that he is late because the tire got punctured; you are already yelling at him. So, understand each other. So, maybe this is the hardest thing for a teacher to look at before you scold them.” – IDI-05

“The lessons that I gained are that, as an instructor, you need to be open-minded, and acceptance is still there. Although the students will be different in the way they show the treatment to you, you still need to remember what they are showing now, maybe because they are already influenced, especially in the media, and they have already applied it to themselves. But still, the students should be reminded.” – IDI-06

“My lesson is to be understanding on the part of the students, especially because it is a local college and the students, the learners, are from diverse communities and diverse cultures. So, they are also different from those students from rural areas and cities.” – IDI-07

Upholding Professionalism and Respect with Each Other

“Not all students have the same backgrounds and experiences. So, as the instructor, we must not be insensitive; we must be understanding, but you must not allow yourself to be down; you are always above the students, but with respect to each other. I have gained lessons from my student on how to handle a situation. For example, when he is angry, how should I handle him? Will I be angry too? Are we both angry? So, if that is the case, there will be war. You, the teacher, listen to his side, about life, and then I will answer. Because what I did before was wrong, I immediately responded without hearing his side, so now there is a conflict with my student. With that, it should be changed to be an active listener and give advice to students.” – IDI-11

“I would like to advise them that as a KCAST student, they need to respect not only the instructors but the KCAST personnel as well. Because sometimes the students, when they think you are just a staff or just a utility, sometimes they do not give respect, even saying good morning, ma’am, good afternoon, ma’am, good evening, sir, like that. Wherever you go or whom you are talking with, you should not forget the respect.” – IDI-06

“Number one is to always be polite with your instructor. It's not just that they are your instructors; it does not mean that you are formal. But it's because, regardless of what position that person has, especially if it's academic, you have to maintain formality and professionalism.” – IDI-09

“They should learn how to communicate formally, not only in the classroom; it is also a practice. Probably, as they graduate, they will become professionals already, and it is very important to know how to communicate. Even if we say you do not know the person, there are times where you can tell just by communicating with them that he is a professional because he knows you communicate and everything. So, at least it's also a practice for them to really learn how to become good communicators, at least in the classroom itself.” – IDI-10

“Whoever you meet, regardless of whether he is a janitor or something, you must maintain respect for everyone. Do not choose whom you are going to respect.” – IDI-14

Build a Healthy Relationship in the Learning Environment

“In order to maintain the positive influence of the students, you have to make friends with them and understand them. Because our generation is different, their generation is also different, so you have to understand why they are like this. If they are more active on social media, then you are too. You should go with the trend. You can use them to catch their attention and bring your heart closer to them because the more the children's hearts are far from yours, the more they won't respect you. That is what I have learned. When we are outside, we have a great vibe. But when inside, their respect for me remained.” – IDI-03

“I am totally strict; I will say that I am strict with my students. Maybe talk to them slowly, because if you are always strict, that is how I realized that if you're strict, students won't approach you, but students will approach me because you smile too. But for me, I always maintain a positive relationship because I will bring back the mood after I scold the child, after I say hurtful words.” – IDI-05

“It is very important that, once you are a teacher, you make sure that the atmosphere inside the classroom is good. So, how will you make sure that the atmosphere in the classroom is good? So first, you have to secure a student-teacher relationship. You must ensure that there is respect between the teacher and student, and you must also not let yourself, as a teacher, let the students think that they should be afraid of you; they should not be. It is very important that this is the kind of relationship where respect is there.” – IDI-06

“Having formal correspondence in communication is very important because this is how you should maintain your relationship with other people. If you were to show your wrong actions to other people, those people whom you are talking to might cut you off from having conversations with them or lose interest in interacting with you. So, in this situation, it is important that you maintain your formality, even though you still have that kind of formality. Being formal means that you are not going to offend somebody, which will cause you problems when dealing with people.” – IDI-13

“When you teach, you do not always take it seriously because the children are like stubborn candles that they do not understand. They cannot understand anymore because they are afraid of your look, so you have to adjust. If you think that everything is very serious, you will switch your strategy to keep the barangay kabataan alive and well.” – IDI-14

To Lead is to Set by Example

The theme emphasizes the importance of leading through one's own actions and behaviors rather than just words. It highlights that teachers serve as influential figures in the lives of their students, and they have the opportunity to shape their students' attitudes and actions through their own conduct. The college instructors have realized and learned that they should be role models to their students, and where they exhibit certain behaviors, such as respect, they must demonstrate those behaviors themselves. Moreover, by setting a positive example, teachers not only establish credibility and earn respect from their students but also create a supportive and positive learning environment. With this, students are more likely to emulate the behaviors they see demonstrated by their teachers, making the teacher's own conduct a powerful tool for fostering desired qualities and attitudes among students.

From the interview, Gentle (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of mutual respect between teachers and students in maintaining effective communication and fostering a positive learning environment. He emphasizes that respect is a foundational element in the teacher-student dynamic. When students feel respected by their teachers, they are more likely to engage actively in the learning process,

feel valued, and be receptive to instruction. Likewise, when teachers feel respected by their students, they are better able to establish authority, maintain discipline, and effectively convey information. Gentle (pseudonym) stated:

“Isa sa akong gusto ma emphasize, og ipakita sa imoha, isulti is the respect gyud. Ma maintain gyud diha. Pag once nga gina respeto ang estudyante and at the same time vice versa, the instructor respect by the students. For me, for sure, ma maintain jud ang effective communication sa estudyante once ma implement na siyang maayo.” (IDI-01)

(One of the things I want to emphasize, show, or say is respect. Once the student is respected and, at the same time, vice versa, the instructor is respected by the student, effective communication with the student can be maintained once it is well implemented.)

As with the other participant, Attentive Observer (pseudonym) pointed out that instructors need to be mindful of the way they communicate with students. She suggests that teachers should uphold a level of professionalism in their interactions, reminding students of the teacher-student relationship and maintaining appropriate levels of respect and authority. Thus, by demonstrating professionalism, respect, and adherence to boundaries in their own interactions with students, teachers set a standard for appropriate conduct. She said:

“Sa part naman sa instructor is siguro sa akong makita is unsaon pud nila pag communicate ang mga student’s kay based lang pud sa akong observation, naa man pud gud mga instructors nga murag when it comes to the communication that they have with the students murag casual lang kaayo ba murag wala na sila naka set didto og boundaries gud na kanang hala oy teacher diay ko, student diay nako ni. Kinahanglan pud ma remind ang instructors nga naa pud ka dapat boundary when it comes to the communication that you have with your students. Ang danger man gud diha is kadto ng too much comfortable na kaayo sa imoha ang students.” (IDI-04)

(On the instructor's part, what I can see maybe is how they communicate with the students, because based on my observation, there are also instructors who seem to be casual when it comes to the communication they have with the students. It is like they did not set any boundaries there. I am a teacher, and you are my student. The instructors should also be reminded that you also have boundaries when it comes to the communication that you have with your students. The danger is that the students are too comfortable with you. So, now, instead of that, they will address you in a proper way.)

Additionally, Empowering (pseudonym) highlighted the importance of maintaining formalities and professionalism in communication, regardless of whether one is a teacher or a student. It highlights that the expectations of respectful and formal communication apply to both parties and should not be disregarded. Empowering (pseudonym) also stresses that maintaining professionalism in communication with students reinforces their authority, establishes clear boundaries, and fosters a conducive learning environment. It sets a positive example for students to emulate and helps to uphold the integrity of the teacher-student relationship. She pointed:

“Whether teacher or student ka man, dapat yung formalities andon parin wag walain yung formality when it comes to communication either media man yan, or face-to-face. Most especially professional ka na, where ever you go, professional jud ka. So, maskin kinsa man na imong ka storya, dapat magpakita jud kag professionalism.” (IDI-06)

(Whether you are a teacher or a student, the formalities should still be there. Do not leave out the formality when it comes to communication, whether via media or face-to-face. Most especially, you are a professional; wherever you go, you are a professional. So, no matter who you are talking to, you should show professionalism.)

Moreover, Welcoming (pseudonym) emphasizes the reciprocal nature of respect between teachers and students, highlighting the responsibility of instructors to model respectful behavior in order to cultivate respect from their students. She emphasized that respect begins with the instructor's own actions and demeanor. She mentioned:

“Mag start jud na sa ikaw nga pagka instructor. Let say for example, imoha siyang estudyante, ni chat sa imoha bla bla bla dayon unya imong replyan og good evening. So, ma ano ra dayon na siya ay good evening diay ma'am. Ang akoo ba is unsaon nato pag ano og respect sa atoaang mga estudyante kung ikaw mismo dili kabalo mu respeto sa imong mga estudyante.” (IDI-09)

(It starts with you and who you are as an instructor. Let us say, for example, that he is your student, he chats with you, and then you reply, good evening. So, he will reply, good evening, ma'am. For me, how can students respect you if you yourself do not know how to respect them.)

Furthermore, Guiding Beacon (pseudonym) pointed out that a teacher sets an example by consistently demonstrating respectful behavior in their communication and interactions with others. He believed that by embodying these values themselves, they could influence their students to adopt similar behaviors. In addition, Guiding Beacon (pseudonym) emphasized that respect is a two-way street. They understand that in order to receive respect from their students, they must first show respect to them. He stated:

“I maintain formality in making communications with my students or even engaging with them by making myself an example of myself in formality or dealing with people. So, I started showing respect to my students, and they must follow as well. With that, I guess they will see it, and I also wanted to make them do the actions of being polite and respectful.” (IDI-13)

Lastly, Approachable (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of teachers setting a positive example for their students in order to earn respect. She highlights that the way teachers interact with their students plays a crucial role in shaping how students perceive and respond to them. Moreover, Approachable (pseudonym) asserts that teachers should treat their students with kindness and respect if

they expect to receive the same treatment in return. She shared:

“Dapat the way ka mo deal sa imong estudyante in a nice way pud para marespetohan sad ka nila. Sa imoha gyud kay unsa man imohang e expect sa estudyante nga ipakita nila sa imoha nga ikaw mismo dili ka ka respeto-respeto. So, sa imo gyud na mag start sa unsa nimo pag present imong kaugalingon sa ilaha.” (IDI-14)

(You should deal with your students in a nice way so that they will respect you. It really starts with you: What do you expect from the students that they will show you when you yourself do not deserve to be respected? It really begins with you and how you will present yourself to them.)

The Importance of Open Communication and Sense of Empathy

The theme emphasizes the vital role of open communication and empathy in the relationship between college instructors and students. It encourages instructors to create an environment where students feel safe expressing their thoughts and emotions without fear of judgment. By actively listening and validating students' feelings, instructors foster trust and understanding, paving the way for meaningful interactions and supportive learning experiences. Additionally, cultivating empathy allows instructors to connect with students on a deeper level, recognizing and addressing their individual needs and challenges. By building connections beyond the academic realm and demonstrating care and respect for students, instructors create a sense of belonging and community that enhances the overall college experience. Overall, prioritizing open communication and empathy fosters a positive and inclusive learning environment where students feel valued and empowered to succeed.

During the interview, Gentle (pseudonym) emphasized his commitment to creating a non-judgmental atmosphere where students feel comfortable and valued. He aims to achieve this by communicating to students that they are equals in the classroom, rather than adopting an authoritative or superior stance. By positioning himself as a peer rather than a superior. In addition, he emphasized and recognized that maintaining a positive teacher-student dynamic is essential for effective learning and communication. He also highlights the potential negative consequences of adopting a harsh or intimidating demeanor, emphasizing the importance of fostering a connection based on mutual respect and understanding. Gentle (pseudonym) shared:

“I am very open. Pag naa ko sa klase akong ginapasabot, gina emphasize sa ilaha nga sa classroom, dili ko maghimo nga mag judge nila, mag down nila, like himuon nga ubos sila sa akua. I maintain that one through siguro making myself level with them. Mura ba'g try nakog paubos akong kaugalingon at the level of them nga mas dili sila mataha, ma intimidate or something na ilahan ang among communication ma maintain ang good communication. Kay kung ipa implement nako nga terror kayo ko, ing-ana ka kuan dako jud ang tendency nga malahi jud ang amoang connection and regard with the correspondence itself.” (IDI-01)

(I am very open. When I am in class, I explain and emphasize to them that in the classroom, I do not judge them or put them down, like make them inferior to me. I maintain that one by maybe making myself level with them. It is like if I try to lower myself to their level so that they will not be shy, intimidated, or something, so that our communication can maintain good communication. Because if I implement that and terrorize you, there is a big tendency that our connection and regard for the correspondence itself will be different.)

As with the other participant, Attentive Observer (pseudonym) pointed out the importance of empathy and understanding towards students, recognizing and addressing their individual needs and circumstances. He acknowledges the tendency among some instructors to quickly judge students based on their behavior or performance, emphasizing the need for patience and empathy in such situations. Thus, drawing from personal experiences, Attentive Observer (pseudonym) emphasized the value of taking the time to understand students' unique backgrounds, challenges, and experiences. She stated:

“I really have to understand my students. Naay times where in ang uban na mga instructors ba if they see nga ah ingon ani akong estudyante, diritso man gud dayon mo judge gud at times nga ah kana siya dili gyud dayon kasabot, ah kana siya ingon ana gyud na siya nga student. So, what I have learned from the experiences is that I really have to understand my student's kay basin diay to unyag kani siya nga student is naa ni siyag gipagdaan that is why ing-ana iyahang behavior.” (IDI-04)

(I really have to understand my students. There are times when the other instructors see that, like, my student is like this; they judge right away, or they do not understand right away. So, what I have learned from the experiences is that I really have to understand my student's because maybe that is how he is or he is going through something in life that results from his behavior.)

In addition, Welcoming (pseudonym) suggests that one way to maintain student engagement is to create an atmosphere where students feel comfortable asking questions and expressing their concerns without fear of judgment. By being approachable, open-minded, and responsive to students' needs and inquiries, instructors can demonstrate their commitment to supporting and facilitating student learning. She also highlights that when students feel valued and supported by their teacher, they are more likely to actively participate in class, take risks, and engage in the learning process. She mentioned:

“You have to build rapport and connection with your students. Para sa akua, one of the ano gyud to maintain the engagement of the students if they are afraid to perform in your class, they are not afraid to ask question, or open minded as to and not just open minded but be always cater their concerns in your class. Kay kung ma feel man gud sa imong estudyante nga kung unsa ka mo deal sa ilaha ba, mo follow, naman gud na ang engagement nila. Kay kung mahadlok ang imong mga estudyante sa imoha then the more na sila

mahadlok mo engage, mahadlok na na sila mamali. So, ing-ana siguro, dapat e address nato na oh nga mura bag dapat naa gyud tay connection with your students.” (IDI-09)

(You have to build rapport and connections with your students. For me, one of the ways to maintain the engagement of the students is if they are afraid to perform in your class, they are not afraid to ask questions, or they are open-minded, and not just open-minded, but always cater to their concerns in your class. Because once the students feel how you deal with them, everything will follow, and they will be engaged. Because if your students are afraid of you, then the more they will be afraid to engage, the more they will be afraid to make mistakes. So, that's probably what we should address. We should really have a connection with your students.)

Lastly, Balance (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of creating a supportive and trusting environment for students by ensuring that their feelings and concerns are acknowledged and respected. She prioritizes validating students' emotions and making them feel comfortable approaching them with any issues or questions they may have. Thus, Balance (pseudonym) aims to establish themselves as approachable figures in their students' eyes, communicating a willingness to listen, understand, and support them without judgment or bias. She shared:

“I always make sure that their feelings and concerns will not be invalidated, and I will let them feel that they can always come to me or talk to me. Let me say establishing an image of being approachable, but I do not know if that's how they perceive it, but I am trying to do that by communicating it to them. They can be open with me, they can be honest with me, and they would be free from any possible judgment or biases that they would be hearing unless the particular issue or concern has been treated or has been approached properly.” (IDI-12)

The Value of Cultivating Good Connections through Understanding, Consideration, and Openness

The theme highlights the importance of fostering positive relationships built on empathy, respect, and transparency. It emphasizes the significance of actively seeking to understand others, being considerate of their feelings and perspectives, and maintaining an open and honest dialogue. This means that educators should place a high value on developing a personal connection with each student and acknowledging and honoring their unique needs and experiences. Teachers may foster a welcoming and inclusive learning atmosphere where students feel appreciated, valued, and empowered to achieve by modeling empathy, consideration, and openness in their interactions. Furthermore, maintaining this fosters effective communication, collaboration, and mutual respect, all of which eventually lead to a positive and enriching educational experience for all involved.

During the interview, Gentle (pseudonym) emphasized the critical role of effective and formal communication in fostering a strong connection between students and instructors. Gentle (pseudonym) asserts that maintaining clear and respectful communication sets the foundation for a positive relationship between teachers and students. Moreover, he highlighted that when communication is open and effective, students feel comfortable expressing their concerns and sharing their experiences with their instructors. Conversely, if communication is lacking or ineffective, students may hesitate to communicate their problems or feelings, leading to potential issues being overlooked or ignored. Gentle (pseudonym) stated:

“For me lang, importante jud ang effective, formal communication jud sa student and instructor connection. Why? Kay pag ma maintain na siya, the rest will follow. Pag as long as good inyong communication, good inyong connection, estudyante og sa teacher, actually kung unsa man gud ang mga concern mga mulo sa imohang estudyante, manggawas gyud na like kana bitaw naa something nga nagpaka hilom lang, hantod nga dili good ilahang communication, nagka problema niya wala kabalo ang instructor nga ing-ani diay problema niya kay wala man dili man open. Kana lang gyud be open noh nga mahitabo ang imong mga estudyante, mu undang nalang, mu hawa nalang. Pero para sa akoo lang gyud, ang instructor ang dakog responsibility.” (IDI-01)

(For me, effective, formal communication is important in the student-instructor connection. Why? Because when it is maintained, the rest will follow. As long as your communication is good, your connection is good, student and teacher; actually, whatever concerns your students say, they will come out. Until it comes to the point that students will be quiet, the communication is not good, students already have a problem, and the instructor did not know that this was his problem because there was no open communication. That is the only way to be open with your students. For me, instructors have the biggest responsibility in terms of that.)

As with the other participant, Compassionate Caretaker (pseudonym) highlights the importance of patience, love, and empathy in the role of a teacher. She pointed out that teachers must exhibit patience and genuine care for their students in order to support their success. She reflects on instances where students appeared disengaged or tired in class. In that situation, by demonstrating love and concern for their students, Compassionate Caretaker (pseudonym) was able to establish a connection and gain the attention of the students. This led to providing appropriate support to the students. She stated:

“Akoang mga insights nga akoang mahatag kay dapat ang maestra kanang maging pasensoso. Dapat naa kay gugma sa imong mga students kasi pag dili nimo love, dali ra kaayo sila ibagsak. Pwede na nimo sila ingnan nga basak ka dinhia. Kasi may mga panahon nga ga klase ko naay gapanguy-ab, magklase ko tulogan lang ko. As their instructor, akoo gyud na silang gina love, ako na silang ginapangutana noh unsay ilang problema, kay tungod pud ana na gain nako ang ilahang attention na si ma'am gapa minaw diay sa akoo, naa jud diay ni problema. Kasi one time, naay bata ba nga ako jud siya gipangutana kay sigi lang siyag tulog sa akoo klase noh problema diay niya is tungod diay sa ilang ka pobre, working students siya. Kana ba, dapat ang instructor considerate pud.” (IDI-03)

(My insights that I can give are that the teacher should be patient. You must have love for your students, because if you do not love them, it is very easy to let them fail. Because there are times when I am in class, students are already yawning, and some are sleeping. As their instructor, I learned to really love them. I ask them what their problem is, and because of that, I got their attention—that ma'am is listening to me. It turns out they have a problem. One time, there was a child that I asked because he kept sleeping in my class, but his problem was because they were poor; he was a working student. In that case, the instructor should be considerate too.)

In addition, Attentive Observer (pseudonym) explained the importance of understanding and patience in the role of an instructor, particularly when it comes to communication with students from diverse backgrounds. As a result, instructors must recognize that students may have varying levels of proficiency in formal communication skills. Attentive Observer (pseudonym) advocates for understanding and patience from instructors in teaching students the proper ways of communicating. This involves recognizing and respecting the unique backgrounds and experiences of students and providing support and guidance as needed. She stated:

“Balikon nako to ang understanding. Dili man tanan students gikan og mga the term high end na mga schools in order for them to understand right away. Naa man tay students gyud nga gikan pa didto sa mga areas where in nga basig wala jud kaayo na sa ila na instill kung unsa ang formal communication. That is why, we need to understand and maging patient lang gyud mi nga instructor in order for us to really teach them kung unsaon ang proper ways of communication.” (IDI-04)

(I will say it again, understanding. Students are not the same as those who came from high-end schools in order to understand right away. There are some students in areas where maybe formal communication is not emphasized. That is why we need to understand and be patient as instructors in order to teach them the proper ways of communicating.)

Moreover, Nurturing (pseudonym) highlights the importance of empathy and understanding in the teacher-student relationship, particularly in moments of conflict or discipline. He mentioned that both teachers and students are humans and therefore susceptible to mistakes and misunderstandings. Rather than solely resorting to scolding or disciplinary action, teachers should adopt a more empathetic approach that involves open communication and mutual understanding. He shared:

“At the end of the day, tao ra gihapon ta, ang estudyante tao ra pud. Human nimo makasab-an, kung mahiubos siya nimo, you need to talk noh. Ang lesson lang gyud na imong understanding by each other noh. Kung estudyante nimo siya, human nimo makasab-an kay late siya, nganong na late siya so, naa didto ang end point nga ay na late siya kay tungod kay noh tungod kay na platan diay siya niya nangasaba na ka sa iyaha. So, understanding each other noh. So, maybe mao nay pinaka bug-at nga tan-awon ni teacher nga dapat before ka mangasaba, ako, mangasaba man pud jud ko.” (IDI-05)

(At the end of the day, we are still humans, and the student is also human. After you scold him, if you get him down, you need to talk. The only lesson you can learn is to understand each other. If he is your student, after you scolded him for being late, why is he late? There is the end point that he is late because the tire got punctured; you are already yelling at him. So, understand each other. So, maybe this is the hardest thing for a teacher to look at before you scold them.)

Meanwhile, Empowering (pseudonym) shared the importance of open-mindedness and acceptance in the role of an instructor, particularly when it comes to understanding and addressing the behavior of students. She also mentioned that some students may exhibit behaviors that are influenced by external factors such as media, thus, it is essential for instructors to understand and acknowledge these differences rather than immediately passing judgment. By remaining open-minded and accepting, instructors can create a supportive and inclusive learning environment where students feel respected and valued for their individuality. She said:

“The lessons that I gained is that, as an instructor, you need to be open minded and acceptance is andon parin. Though magka-lahilahi ang students the way they pakita ang treatment sa imoha, but still, you need to remember na kung unsa man na ang ilang gina pakita karon, maybe because na impluwensyahan na na siya most especially sa media and na apply na pud na nila sa ilahang self. Pero still, dapat e remind ra gihapon ang mga students.” (IDI-06)

(The lessons that I gained are that, as an instructor, you need to be open-minded, and acceptance is still there. Although the students will be different in the way they show the treatment to you, you still need to remember what they are showing now, maybe because they are already influenced, especially in the media, and they have already applied it to themselves. But still, the students should be reminded.)

Furthermore, Cultural Compassionate (pseudonym) highlights the importance of understanding and accommodating the diverse backgrounds and cultures of students, particularly in the context of a local college with learners from various communities and cultural backgrounds. This involves being sensitive to the cultural norms, beliefs, and values of students, as well as recognizing the potential challenges they may face as they navigate their educational journey. She stated:

“Akoang lesson is be understanding sa part sa students especially kay it is a local college and ang mga students, ang learners if from diverse community and diverse culture. So, magka iba din sila sa kadtong mga students from rural and cities.” (IDI-07)

(My lesson is to be understanding on the part of the students, especially because it is a local college and the students, the learners, are from diverse communities and diverse cultures. So, they are also different from those students from rural areas and cities.)

Lastly, Empathetic (pseudonym) shared valuable lessons learned from a student interaction, highlighting the importance of effective

communication and conflict resolution. In addition, she also highlights that not all students come from the same circumstances, and it is essential for instructors to avoid being insensitive or dismissive of these differences. Instead, instructors should strive to be understanding and empathetic toward their students while maintaining a respectful and authoritative role. She shared:

“Dili jud tanan estudyante pare-parehas og mga kaagi. So, kita as an instructor, dili ta maging insensitive, dapat magpa bilin nga masinabunon, pero dili jud ka magpa daog-daog. Always jud ka above sa students pero with respect to each other. Naka gain ko og lessons sa akong estudyante on how to handle a situation, for example nga nasuko siya, so unsaon nako siya pag handle. Masuko pud ba ko? Masuko ba ming duha? So, mag war na. Ikaw nga teacher, maminaw ka sa iyang mga lumo sa kinabuhi and tsaka na nako mutubag. Kay sa una man gud, mutubag dayon ko so mag away na mi sa akong estudyante. So, kadto, mali gyud to akong gi buhat. Dapat mabag-o to siya og active listening, listener jud si teacher then maghatag pud siya og advice sa student.” (IDI-11)

(Not all students have the same backgrounds and experiences. So, as the instructor, we must not be insensitive; we must be understanding, but you must not allow yourself to be down; you are always above the students, but with respect to each other. I have gained lessons from my student on how to handle a situation. For example, when he is angry, how should I handle him? Will I be angry too? Are we both angry? So, if that is the case, there will be war. You, the teacher, listen to his side, about life, and then I will answer. Because what I did before was wrong, I immediately responded without hearing his side, so now there is a conflict with my student. With that, it should be changed to be an active listener and give advice to students.)

Upholding Professionalism and Respect with Each Other

The theme explores the importance of maintaining a culture of dignity, integrity, and mutual respect within educational environments. It emphasized the significance of demonstrating professionalism and respect in interactions not only between instructors and students but also among all members of the educational community. Moreover, this also highlights the expectation for students to show respect and professionalism towards their instructors. This involves addressing instructors respectfully, following academic guidelines and standards, and showing courtesy. By demonstrating respect for their instructors, students contribute to a positive and conducive learning environment and foster a healthy teacher-student relationship based on mutual respect and trust.

During the interview, Empowering (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of showing respect to all members of the academic community, including instructors and personnel, within KCAST. She highlights that students should recognize and value the contributions of all individuals within the institution, regardless of their position or role. Thus, by emphasizing the importance of respect towards all individuals, they can foster a culture of inclusivity, appreciation, and professionalism within the institution. She stated:

“I would like to advise them na as a KCAST student, they need to respect not just only the instructors but the KCAST personnel also. Kasi sometimes man gud ang mga students, pag tingin nila staff ka lang or utility ka lang, sometimes, wala na nila ginahatagan og respect even saying good morning, ma'am, good afternoon, ma'am, good evening, sir, ingon ana. Whether nasa labas ka man, or baskin mga normal person ka lang, dapat wag walain yung respect.” (IDI-06)

(I would like to advise them that as a KCAST student, they need to respect not only the instructors but the KCAST personnel as well. Because sometimes the students, when they think you are just a staff or just a utility, sometimes they do not give respect, even saying good morning, ma'am, good afternoon, ma'am, good evening, sir, like that. Wherever you go or whom you are talking with, you should not forget the respect.)

Additionally, Welcoming (pseudonym) pointed out the importance of maintaining politeness and professionalism when interacting with instructors, regardless of their position or role within the academic setting. She also mentioned that politeness should be a fundamental aspect of student-instructor interactions, not only because instructors hold a position of authority but also because it is a reflection of professionalism and respect. She said:

“Number one is always be polite with your instructor. It's not just they are your instructors, dili mana mao ang pasabot nga tungod kay instructor nimo ing-ana ka ka pormal. But tungod na siya sa regardless unsa may position ana nga tao noh labi na og academic imohang matter noh so you have to maintain the formality, the professionalism.” (IDI-09)

(Number one is to always be polite with your instructor. It is not just that they are your instructors; it does not mean that you are formal. But it is because, regardless of what position that person has, especially if it is academic, you have to maintain formality and professionalism.)

Moreover, Adaptive (pseudonym) underscores the importance of developing formal communication skills, particularly within the academic setting, as it serves as valuable preparation for students' future professional endeavors. Furthermore, she added that the way individuals communicate can often indicate their level of professionalism. She shared:

“They should learn on how to communicate formally, not only in the classroom but it's also a practice. Probably, as they graduate, they will become professionals already and it is very important to know how to communicate. Baskin pa'g muingon ta og you don't know the person, there are times where in nga makabalo ka pag communicate pa lang nila ah professional ni siya kay kabalo siya mo communicate and everything. So, at least it's also a practice sa ilaha to really learn on how to become a good communicator, at least

by the classroom itself.” (IDI-10)

(They should learn how to communicate formally, not only in the classroom; it is also a practice. Probably, as they graduate, they will become professionals already, and it is very important to know how to communicate. Even if we say you do not know the person, there are times where you can tell just by communicating with them that he is a professional because he knows you communicate and everything. So, at least it is also a practice for them to really learn how to become good communicators, at least in the classroom itself.)

Lastly, Approachable (pseudonym) emphasized the importance of showing respect to everyone, regardless of their occupation, position, or status. She highlights the principle of treating all individuals with dignity and consideration, regardless of their role within society. Furthermore, Approachable (pseudonym) encourages a mindset of inclusivity and empathy, recognizing the inherent worth and contributions of every person. She stated:

“Kung kinsa man na imong kasugat, regardless og janitor ba na siya or unsa, dapat maintain imohang respeto sa tanan tao. Dili pillion, dili mamili ana siya.” (IDI-14)

(Whoever you meet, regardless of whether he is a janitor or something, you must maintain respect for everyone. Do not choose whom you are going to respect.)

Build a Healthy Relationship in the Learning Environment

The theme explores focuses on the vital role of the teacher in building a positive and healthy relationship with their students. They emphasized that building a healthy relationship in the learning environment is crucial as it creates a foundation of trust, respect, and support essential for academic and personal growth. When students feel valued and respected by their teachers, they are more likely to engage actively in the learning process which fosters a sense of belonging and emotional safety, enabling students to express themselves freely, ask questions, and seek help when needed. Moreover, the participants express the importance of great understanding, adjustments, the vital role of communication between teacher and student, and the importance of creating an atmosphere where the students don't feel fear because of their strictness as instructors. Consequently, the theme underscores the profound impact that positive teacher-student relationships have on student learning, well-being, and overall educational experience.

From the interview, Compassionate Caretaker (pseudonym) stated the importance of maintaining a positive influence over students by building a genuine connection with them. She emphasized that understanding the differences between generations is crucial in fostering this connection, particularly in today's digital age where social media plays a significant role. In addition, she also mentioned that immersing oneself in the trends and interests of the students, one can effectively capture their attention and bridge the gap between generations. Compassionate Caretaker (pseudonym) said:

“Para ma maintain ang positive influence sa mga students is imoha silang amigohon, imoha silang sabton. Kasi lahi man gud ang amoang generation, lahi sad ang ilahang generation, so imoha silang sabton nganong ingon ani sila. Kung more on social media sila then go pud ka sa ilaha maging ano pud ka sa social media. Dapat kung unsa ang uso sa ilaha, pwede nimo silang para ma catch ilahang attention and para kanang maduol imong loob sa ilaha kay the more man gud pag ah layo pud ang loob sa mga bata sa imoha the more nga dili ka nila respetuon. Mao na sya akong nasabtan. Pero pag ako naa sa gawas, vibe kaayo mi, ka jive nako ang mga bata. Pero pag naa sa sulod, nag remain ang ilahang pag respeto sa akoo.” (IDI-03)

(In order to maintain the positive influence of the students, you have to make friends with them and understand them. Because our generation is different, their generation is also different, so you have to understand why they are like this. If they are more active on social media, then you are too. You should go with the trend. You can use them to catch their attention and bring your heart closer to them because the more the children's hearts are far from yours, the more they will not respect you. That is what I have learned. When we are outside, we have a great vibe. But when inside, their respect for me remained.)

Additionally, Nurturing (pseudonym) acknowledges being strict with his students but also recognizes the importance of maintaining a balance. He claimed that being overly strict can create a barrier between the teacher and students, making it difficult for students to approach them. Instead, he combined strictness with kindness and approachability. Moreover, Nurturing (pseudonym) believes in restoring the mood and repairing any hurt feelings caused by their strictness, ensuring that the teacher-student relationship remains constructive and supportive. He stated:

“Ako, I am totally strict. Muingon gyud ko nga I'm strict sa akong mga estudyante. Maybe, hinay-hinayon silag storya kay kung isog raman pud ka permente... mao man pud na akong na realized nga pag isog pud ka di jud ka duolan og estudyante pero sa akoo muduol man pud ang mga estudyante kay mag smile man pud ka. Kay kung sa akoo lang I also always maintain with that the positive relation, sa akong ka strikto dapat man gyud paulian nimo ang ang bata human nimo kasab-an, human nimo ma storyahan og sakit imoha gyud siyang dulon nganong nakasab-an nimo siya.” (IDI-05)

(I am totally strict; I will say that I am strict with my students. Maybe talk to them slowly, because if you are always strict, that is how I realized that if you are strict, students will not approach you, but students will approach me because I smile too. But for me, I always maintain a positive relationship despite my strictness, I will bring back the mood after I scold the child, after I say hurtful words.)

Moreover, Empowering (pseudonym) expressed that creating a positive atmosphere within the classroom is paramount for effective

teaching and learning. Central to achieving this is establishing a strong student-teacher relationship based on respect and trust. She stated, as a teacher, it is crucial to foster an environment where students feel comfortable expressing themselves and engaging in discussions without fear of judgment or reprisal. This involves setting clear expectations for behavior and communication while also demonstrating empathy and understanding towards students' perspectives. She stated:

“It is a very important na once teacher ka you have to make it sure na yung atmosphere inside the classroom is maganda. So, how you will make it sure na ang atmosphere sa classroom is maganda. So first, you have to secure student-teacher relationship. Dapat e secure mo na there is a respect between the teacher and student and also, do not let yourself as a teacher nga mahimong... though you are the teacher inside the classroom but still do not let the students na isipin na dapat katakotan ka nila, di dapat ganon. It is very important na kana ganing a kind of relationship nga where in mura gihapon siya og ano pero ang respect andon.” (IDI-06)

(It is very important that, once you are a teacher, you make sure that the atmosphere inside the classroom is good. So, how will you make sure that the atmosphere in the classroom is good? So first, you have to secure a student-teacher relationship. You must ensure that there is respect between the teacher and student, and you must also not let yourself, as a teacher, let the students think that they should be afraid of you; they should not be. It is very important that this is the kind of relationship where respect is there.)

Furthermore, Guiding Beacon (pseudonym) pointed out the significance of fostering a positive classroom atmosphere as a teacher. He highlights the essential steps in achieving this, primarily focusing on establishing a strong student-teacher relationship based on mutual respect. Furthermore, by emphasizing respect as the cornerstone of the teacher-student dynamic, Guiding Beacon (pseudonym) emphasizes the importance of creating a conducive learning environment where students are motivated to engage actively and learn effectively. He shared:

“Having formal correspondence in communication is very important because this is how you should maintain your relationship with other people. If you were to show your wrong actions to other people, those people whom you are talking to might cut you off from having conversations with them or lose interest in interacting with you. So, in this situation, it is important that you maintain your formality, even though you still have that kind of formality. Being formal means that you are not going to offend somebody, which will cause you problems when dealing with people.” (IDI-13)

Lastly, Approachable (pseudonym) explained that when teaching, it is essential not to always take a serious approach because excessive seriousness may intimidate or deter students from engaging with the material. Instead, they should advocate for adapting teaching methods to accommodate students' apprehensions and anxieties. By adjusting one's approach and demeanor, teachers can create a more welcoming and inclusive atmosphere in the classroom. She said:

“Kung mag tudlo ka, dili sa tanang panahon mag seryoso ka kay ang mga bata mura nag gipang ugbok nga kandila nga wala sila kasabot og nakasabot ba na sila og wala. Dili naman na sila maka sabot kay nahadlok na sa imong awra so dapat mag adjust ka. So, kung murag tan-aw nimo nga murag seryoso naman kaayo ang tanan, mag switch na pud ka og strategy nimo nga ma alive-alive ang mga Kabataang barangay.” (IDI-14)

(When you teach, you do not always take it seriously because the children are like stubborn candles that they do not understand. They cannot understand anymore because they are afraid of your look, so you have to adjust. If you think that everything is very serious, you will switch your strategy to keep the Kabataang barangay alive and well.)

Conclusions

In conclusion, the study revealed that the participants had a variety of experiences, such as having language barriers to effective communication, crossing the line between teacher and student relationships, extending service beyond the working hours, struggling in the absence of proper etiquette in dealing with teachers, experiencing a lack of respect from students, and having message misinterpretation on online platforms. Additionally, the participants employed various coping mechanisms, such as setting clear expectations at the beginning of a course or program, correcting improper behavior immediately, establishing boundaries and authority in the class, building good rapport through a supportive teacher-student relationship, having an understanding of the various underlying reasons for student's misbehaviors, implementing a policy of language used inside the classroom, and strengthening student-teacher communication through comprehensive feedback. Furthermore, the participants shared valuable insights regarding the study, emphasizing the importance of leading by example, the importance of open communication and a sense of empathy, the value of cultivating good connections through understanding, consideration, and openness, upholding professionalism and respect with each other, and building a healthy relationship in the learning environment.

The findings of this study show that the college instructors have observed various behaviors among students that impact communication and classroom dynamics. These observations include encountering language barriers that hinder effective communication, witnessing instances where the boundaries between teacher-student relationships become blurred, and facing challenges related to students' expectations for service beyond regular working hours. Additionally, instructors have noted a lack of proper etiquette in students' communication with teachers, such as using informal language or exhibiting disrespectful behavior. Moreover, these observations highlight the complexity of student-teacher interactions and underscore the importance of addressing communication challenges and maintaining professional boundaries within educational settings.

In addition, setting clear expectations at the beginning of a course or program helps establish a framework for communication and behavior, reducing misunderstandings and conflict. Correcting improper behavior immediately reinforces boundaries and expectations, maintaining a respectful and professional classroom environment. Establishing boundaries and authority in the class provides structure and clarity, ensuring that students understand the roles and responsibilities of both teachers and themselves. Building rapport through a supportive teacher-student relationship fosters trust and mutual respect, and facilitating open communication. Understanding the underlying reasons for students' misbehaviors enables instructors to respond with empathy and appropriate support, addressing root causes rather than just symptoms. Implementing a policy of language use inside the classroom sets standards for respectful communication, promoting a positive and inclusive learning environment. Strengthening student-teacher communication through comprehensive feedback encourages dialogue, reflection, and continuous improvement. Overall, these approaches empower college instructors to navigate challenges effectively, maintain professionalism, and foster productive student-teacher formal correspondence.

Moreover, setting an example is important as it emphasizes that teachers lead through their own actions and behaviors rather than just words, as they serve as influential figures in the lives of their students. Recognizing the importance of open communication, teachers understand the necessity of creating a transparent and welcoming environment where students feel comfortable expressing themselves and sharing their thoughts. The value of cultivating good connections through understanding, consideration, and openness allows teachers to approach interactions with students with empathy and patience, facilitating clearer and more respectful communication. Upholding professionalism and respect set a tone of mutual regard and dignity, fostering trust and cooperation in formal communication exchanges. Building healthy relationships in the learning environment establishes a foundation of trust and support, encouraging students to communicate their needs and concerns openly. Overall, by internalizing these principles, teachers can enhance student-teacher formal communication, creating a supportive and conducive learning environment where effective communication thrives.

During my research journey, I encountered various obstacles, but one particular challenge remains memorable: the significant effort I devoted to finding suitable participants for my study. It required a week of thorough searching to identify the right individuals, and unexpected situations caused delays as participants had to reschedule interviews. These delays also posed financial difficulties for me, as commuting from home to school became more costly due to the extended timeline. Despite facing challenges, I find fulfillment in the journey of conducting my study, particularly in getting to know instructors at KCAST and gaining confidence in approaching their offices. I am deeply thankful for the wisdom, knowledge, and physical strength provided by the Lord, which enabled me to persist and successfully complete this study.

Additionally, another challenge I encountered was when my paper was included in the flood, which caused me to pass again and again for ethics without knowing that I already had my certificate of compliance and was ready to conduct my study. Despite facing challenges, I stay hopeful and committed to finishing my study, moving forward despite doubts and overthinking. I am confident in my ability to overcome these challenges, having voiced my intentions and prayers to the Lord and firmly believing that I will successfully complete my research project.

Indeed, this research journey has been a testament to resilience, determination, and the power of faith. Despite encountering numerous challenges, the researcher has emerged stronger, more knowledgeable, and deeply grateful for the invaluable lessons learned along the way. Through perseverance and unwavering faith, she has not only completed this study but has also grown personally and academically. As the researcher finishes this chapter, she is reminded that no challenge is too big if you keep pushing forward. She hopes her work inspires others to chase their dreams with confidence and determination.

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